

Project Management Certificate Program Notes

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Foundations of project management:

- Project management is the application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to meet the project requirements and achieve the desired outcome.
- What is a project: A project, is a unique endeavor, and usually includes a set of unique deliverables. It's also a temporary pursuit. It has a defined beginning and an end.
- PM is important because it helps ensure that a project delivers the expected outcomes, both on time and within budget.
- Preparing for a project you can start with: training, budgeting, communication with other parties and much more.
- Program managers are manager of many projects for a certain product, team, or a program. And the next step is portfolio managers.
- Responsible innovation means innovating while keeping the company's values in mind and achieve the company's goals.
- What a project manager does is: planning and organizing, managing tasks, budgeting, controlling costs and other factors. Everything they do helps make sure the project can be completed on time and on budget.
- A project manager may create a service or modify an old one to better fit the customer's needs.
- An important thing to know about being a project manager is that: You'll use different tools, techniques and methodologies every single day.
- Operation: as an activity or activities performed on a product or service by a single machine or person. Process: a sequence of operations (consisting of people, machines, materials, and methods) for the design, manufacture, and delivery of a product or service.
- Regardless of the industry in which you currently work, you have gained **transferable skills**. Transferable skills are abilities that can be used in many different jobs and career paths. Your transferable skills can likely be utilized in project management roles in many other industries.
- Project managers use their organizational and interpersonal communication skills to successfully manage their projects.
- Project managers add value to their organization in key ways include: prioritization, delegation, and effective communication.
- Prioritization: means give priority to tasks mean which ones are the most important, and breakdown big tasks to smaller steps. And when they do not know which task to give more priority to they'll connect with their teams and with stakeholders to gather information and make a plan.
- Delegation: is matching tasks to individuals who can best complete the work.
- Effective communication: that means This refers to being transparent, which means being up front with plans and ideas and making information readily available. They keep in regular contact with their team about the progress of the work and help identify areas where a teammate may need support.

- A senior program manager thinks “I think the funnest part about being a project manager is really working with people. You get to meet all different kinds of people, different personalities”.
- Main ways for project managers to add value to organization:
 - focusing on the customer.
 - building a great team.
 - Fostering relationships and communication.
 - managing the project
 - Breaking down barriers.
- In project management, the word “customer” refers to a person or an organization that defines the requirements of the project and sets important guidelines, such as budget and deadlines. And they can be internal such as organization management or team members, or external such as consumers or contractors which is from outside of the organization. And to add value a project manager has to clearly understand customer’s expectations and satisfy them with the results.
- And to communicate with the customers may ask questions like:
 - o What is the problem you would like us to help solve?
 - o How is the problem impacting your organization?
 - o What prompted you to ask for help now?
 - o What is your hope for the outcome of this project?
- The team is a project’s biggest assets. You must understand their motivations, strengths and weaknesses, and get a team with the right skills.
- The project managers who add the most value are the ones who take the time to build relationships, communicate, and treat others with consideration and respect.
- A successful project manager sees the impacts of each process within the project and communicates those impacts to the team. For them to know their roles and see the big picture.
- A project manager adds value to a project when they break down barriers, allow their team to innovate new ways to do things, and empower them to share ideas. As a project manager, you have to model ingenuity and collaboration, and encourage your team to do the same.
- **More about project manager’s roles and responsibilities:**
- Planning and organizing: One responsibility that falls under the umbrella of planning and organizing is making use of productivity tools and creating processes. And create other types of documentations and schedules.
- Budgeting and controlling costs and other factors: This will require you to monitor and manage the budget, track issues and risks as they arise, and manage quality by mitigating those issues and risks. removing unforeseen barriers that come up.
- Managing tasks: A project task is an activity that needs to be accomplished within a set period of time by you, your team, or your stakeholders. Keeping track of tasks helps manage the team's workload and ensure that things are getting done. also a great tool for demonstrating progress to people outside the immediate team, like your stakeholders.

- What are interpersonal skills: **Interpersonal skills** are the behaviors you use to interact with others, such as communication, active listening, and leadership.
- Project managers responsibilities that **utilize interpersonal skills:**
- Teaching and mentoring: When you take the time to fully explain the expectations, you eliminate rework, confusion, and frustration. also involves supporting each individual on your team.
- Building relationships: Relationships are everything! Getting to know your team members lets them know that you care about them as people, not just as employees. Pay attention to the insights they offer you about their work style since their actions can inform how to most effectively interact with them.
- Controlling change: As a project manager, you need to remain flexible and adjust to the stakeholders' needs. However, it is also important to protect your team from constant change and rework. A good way to do this is by documenting.
- Empowering your team: Giving your team the ability to work directly with the stakeholders and their teams lets them know that you trust and believe in their skills! Another way you can empower your team is by delegating responsibilities to them.
- Communicating status and concerns: With effective communication, you can work together with your team to find solutions to challenges.
- A project manager within a team: Everyone on your team will have their own set of roles and responsibilities. And you'll come together to ensure that everyone is able to do their part to advance the project. you won't be an expert in every project role, you'll need to understand and help teammates adopt the right workflows and project management styles. you'll need to collaborate with other teams at the organization to meet the requirements based on project, scope, schedule, and budget.
- **cross-functional teams:** A cross-functional team includes team members who have different backgrounds, types of expertise, and job functions. members of a cross-functional team are referred to as "T-shaped professionals.", for a project manager working in a cross-functional team it is important to:

- clarify goals.
- get team members with the right skills.

- measure progress: Take the time to measure and communicate the project's progress across the cross-functional team. This helps everyone see the full picture and recognize their impact on the project.

- recognize efforts: it is your job to make sure that each member of your cross-functional team recognizes the value of their efforts each step of the way.

- A senior engineering program manager says:" What I do to stay organized is lists, all day long. I have post-it notes, I have electronic lists, I have lists in e-mails". And "I think the thing that makes me a great project manager is a bias to action and resilience."
- Project manager core skillsets: 1enabling dicision-making,2communicating and escalating, 3flexibility, 4organizational skills.
- "The only constant is change"

- Empowering your team or asking the management to express their opinions and make their decisions, allows you to focus on the overarching management tasks, and you can enable them for example by providing relevant data.
- Clear communication and knowing the right time for escalation is important to success. When escalation is required, try to approach management with both the problem and the potential solution or suggestions.
- All project managers need the ability to adapt and overcome changes and challenges, because Change is inevitable, you need to plan flexibly and that's by:
 - o **Assess external constraints:** such as national holidays and team member vacations and sick leave.
 - o **Plan for risks and challenges:** what if someone on your team gets sick or decides to quit.
 - o **Calculate "float" in your schedule:** Float, or slack, refers to the amount of time you can wait to begin a task before it impacts the project schedule and threatens the project outcome.
- Handling ambiguity by:
 - Keep calm
 - Express empathy
 - Communicate what you know clearly
 - Make decisions and stick to them
 - Trust the expertise of your team
- Project managers hire the experts and help put all the pieces of the project together. Project managers don't need to be experts in every field.
- You do not have to know every single detail about the project at all times.
- people do not have to have a lot of experience within an organization to manage projects successfully.
- influencing without authority, which refers to a project manager's ability to guide teammates to complete their assigned work without acting as their direct managers. And that can be done by: communication, negotiation, conflict mediation, and understanding motivations, work ethic.
- you'll need to use your negotiation skills often with your teammates and stakeholders to balance their needs and what is best for the project.
- **Project life cycle:** which means the structure of the project, the four major phases of a project are:
 - Initiate the project
 - Make a plan
 - Execute and complete tasks
 - Close the project
- In the initiation phase you'll define project goals and deliverables, identify the budget and resources you'll need, the people involved in your project, and any other details that can impact the successful completion of your project. And You'll document all this information. and hopefully get approval to move forward with it.
- Planning includes but not limited to: a budget, a breakdown of all the tasks that you need to be completed, ways to communicate team roles and responsibilities, a schedule, resources, and what to do in case your project encounters problems or needs to change.

- During execution your role's a little different. While you might be in charge of completing certain tasks in the project, your primary tasks are to monitor progress and keep your team motivated. You also remove any obstacles that might come up.
- It's important to close the project because one big reason is so your team has a moment to celebrate all of their hard work. Closing the project is also a chance to evaluate how the project went. Closing the project is also a great way to connect with anyone outside your team who may have had interest in the project's goal.

Example project:

- Initiating the project:
 - o discuss project goals with customers to gain a clear understanding of what they are asking for.
 - o gather the stakeholders and project team members to define what needs to be done.
 - o identify the skill sets required, the timeline, and the cost to develop the project. identify and document the value that this project creates for the company.
 - o Get the leadership approval on all the information then get the customer's approval.
 - Making a plan:
 - o outline the important deadlines and tasks for the project to be successful.
 - o create a schedule to account for all resources, materials, and tasks needed to complete the project.
 - Executing and completing tasks:
 - o The project team puts the plan in motion by executing the work.
 - o monitor the team as they complete project tasks.
 - o Help break down any barriers that would slow or stop the team from completing their tasks.
 - o communicate schedule and quality expectations.
 - o keep customers up to date on the project status and gather feedback from them.
 - Closing the project:
 - o complete the project, and deliver it to the customers.
 - o discuss and document with the team the lessons learned from the project. What worked well, and what could work better next time?
 - o put together a small lunch gathering for the team to celebrate and recognize their hard work.
- during the initiation phase you do many thing one of which, count available resources: Resources can include people, equipment, software programs, vendors, physical space or locations, and more. Anything you need to actually complete the project is considered a resource.
- during planning phase: - you create a budget. - set a schedule. - establish your team. - determine roles and responsibilities. - plan for risk and change. - establish communications.
- at the execution phase, communication is important and escalation is possible to be needed, while in case there is changes to be made you need to be flexible to make them.

- on the closing: make sure that the customer is satisfied, all the tasks have been completed, including any work that was added along the way. Be sure any outstanding invoices have been paid, resources are returned and accounted for, and project documentation has been submitted.

- retrospective, it's a chance to note best practices and learn how to manage your project more effectively next time.

- stakeholders are people who are interested in and affected by the project's completion and success. Depending on the type of project, stakeholders could include a department or organization's management team, clients or customers of your product or service, users of your new tool or process, or even the community at large

- pro tip, if in doubt, err on the side of overcommunication.

- project management approaches: A project management methodology is a set of guiding principles and processes for owning a project through its life cycle. The method can be linear (with one task completed before the next can begin) or iterative (with some tasks happening at the same time). Types of approaches are: - Linear means the previous phase or task has to be

completed before the next can start. would work well for a project like building a house. It's less flexible

- iterative, more flexible approach where some of the phases in tasks will overlap or happen at the same time that other tasks are being worked on. like producing a new show for a television company,

- hybrid: at google they encourage everyone to have

Their own way.

- Two of the most popular project management methodologies are Waterfall and Agile.
- Waterfall refers to the sequential ordering of phases. You complete one at a time down the line like a waterfall starting at the top of a mountain and traveling to the bottom. follow an ordered set of steps that are directly linked to clearly defined expectations, resources, and goals that are not likely to change.
- When use Waterfall approach to project management? Well, when the phases of the project are clearly defined or when there are tasks to complete before another can begin, or when changes to the project are very expensive to implement once it's started.
- Waterfall has a linear approach
- The term agile means being able to move quickly and easily. It also refers to flexibility, which means being willing and able to change and adapt.
- Projects that use an Agile approach often have many tasks being worked on at the same time, or in various stages of completion which makes it an iterative approach.
- Agile project phases overlap and tasks are completed in iterations, which in Scrum, are called sprints.

- Agile is more of a mindset than just a series of steps or phases.
- **Waterfall and Agile Comparison**

	Waterfall	Agile
Project manager's role	Project manager serves as an active leader by prioritizing and assigning tasks to team members.	Agile project manager (or Scrum Master) acts primarily as a facilitator, removing any barriers the team faces. Team shares more responsibility in managing their own work.
Scope	Project deliverables and plans are well-established and documented in the early stages of initiating and planning. Changes go through a formal change request process.	Planning happens in shorter iterations and focuses on delivering value quickly. Subsequent iterations are adjusted in response to feedback or unforeseen issues.
Schedule	Follows a mostly linear path through the initiating, planning, executing, and closing phases of the project.	Time is organized into phases called Sprints. Each Sprint has a defined duration, with a set list of deliverables planned at the start of the Sprint.
Cost	Costs are kept under control by careful estimation up front and close monitoring throughout the life cycle of the project.	Costs and schedule could change with each iteration.
Quality	Project manager makes plans and clearly defines criteria to measure quality at the beginning of the project.	Team solicits ongoing stakeholder input and user feedback by testing products in the field and regularly implementing improvements.
Communication	Project manager continually communicates progress toward milestones and other key indicators to stakeholders, ensuring that the project is on track to meet the customer's expectations.	Team is customer-focused, with consistent communication between users and the project team.
Stakeholders	Project manager continually manages and monitors stakeholder engagement to ensure the project is on track.	Team frequently provides deliverables to stakeholders throughout the project. Progress toward milestones is dependent upon stakeholder feedback.

- I would like to put it in this way waterfall is like series connection, while parallel connection is more similar to agile, but not exactly
- Lean Six Sigma It's a combination of two parent methodologies, Lean and Six Sigma. The uses for Lean Six Sigma are common in projects that have goals to save money, improve quality, and

move through processes quickly. It focuses on team collaboration which promotes a positive work environment.

- There are five phases in the Lean Six Sigma approach. They are define, measure, analyze, improve, and control, commonly known as DMAIC.
- what's great about the DMAIC process is that it can be used to solve any business problem.
- This first phase is very similar to the initiation phase of traditional project management.
- In order to improve processes, DMAIC focuses on data.
- you can remember DMAIC like this, defining tells you what to measure, measuring tells you what to analyze, analyzing tells you what to improve, and improving tells you what to control.
- DMAIC ideal when the project goal includes improving the current process to fix complex or high risk problems
- The Lean methodology or lean manufacturing is an approach for removing waste, and adding productivity by that.
- the Lean Manufacturing methodology recognizes eight types of waste within an operation: defects, excess processing, overproduction, waiting, inventory, transportation, motion, and non-utilized talent.
- these types of waste are often attributed to issues such as:
 - Lack of proper documentation
 - Lack of process standards
 - Not understanding the customers' needs
 - Lack of effective communication
 - Lack of process control
 - Inefficient process design
 - Failures of management
- Implement Lean project management when you want to use limited resources, reduce waste, and streamline processes to gain maximum benefits. You can achieve this by using the pillars of the Lean 5S quality tool. refers to the five pillars that are required for good housekeeping: sort, set in order, shine, standardize, and sustain.
- The 5S method includes these five steps:
 - **Sort:** Remove all items not needed for current production operations and leave only the bare essentials.
 - **Set in order:** Arrange needed items so that they are easy to use. Label items so that anyone can find them or put them away.
 - **Shine:** Keep everything in the correct place. Clean your workspace every day.
 - **Standardize:** Perform the process in the same way every time.
 - **Sustain:** Make a habit of maintaining correct procedures and instill this discipline in your team.
- The final concept of Lean uses a **Kanban** scheduling system to manage production.
- **Six Sigma** is a methodology used to reduce variations by ensuring that quality processes are followed every time. generally means that items or processes should have 99.9996% quality.
- The seven key principles of Six Sigma are:
 - Always focus on the customer.
 - Identify and understand how the work gets done. Understand how work really happens.
 - Make your processes flow smoothly.
 - Reduce waste and concentrate on value.

- Stop defects by removing variation.
- Involve and collaborate with your team.
- Approach improvement activity in a systematic way.
- Use this methodology to find aspects of the product or process that are *measurable* like time, cost, or quantity.
- **Scrum** is an Agile framework by which Work is completed by small, cross-functional teams led by a Scrum Master and is divided into short Sprints with a set list of deliverables.
- **Kanban** is both an Agile approach and a tool that provides visual feedback about the status of the work With Kanban, project managers use sticky notes or note cards on a physical or digital Kanban board to represent the team’s tasks with categories like “To do,” “In progress,” and “Done”
- eXtreme programming (XP) methodology is another form of agile project management that was designed for software development.
- The adaptive project framework (APF) methodology, also known as adaptive project management (APM), is a type of agile project management methodology that was designed with the inevitability of change in mind.
- The critical path method (also known as critical path analysis) is a way of identifying and scheduling all of the critical tasks that comprise your project, as well as their dependencies.
- The longest sequence of critical tasks becomes your critical path, and will define the timeframe for your project. Along the path, you’ll have milestones to meet that will signal when one set of tasks (or phase) is over and you can move on to the next one. There are lots of ways to visualize the critical path, depending on the complexity of your project, from flow graphs to Gantt charts.
- Critical chain project management (or CCPM) takes the critical path method (CPM) one step further. While the critical path method defines the length of time needed to get each critical activity done from the beginning of the project to the end, it can often be, well, unrealistic when the time comes to actually put it into practice. Critical chain project management addresses those issues by allowing a bit more time for the human elements of your project — like delays and resourcing issues.
- New product introduction (NPI) is a great project management methodology for when you want to, well, introduce a new product. Also known as new product development (NPD), the new product introduction process covers everything you need to define, develop and launch a new (or improved) product. usually include things like:
 - Defining the product spec and project scope
 - Evaluating the feasibility
 - Developing the prototype
 - Validating the prototype via testing and analysis
 - Manufacturing the product on a larger scale
 - Evaluating the product’s success in the market after launch
- Package enabled reengineering (PER) is a project management methodology that aims to help organizations redesign products or processes with fresh eyes. It focuses on facilitating business transformations quickly and strategically, whether through redesign of processes or realignment of people.
- Outcome mapping is a project progress measurement system, doesn’t focus on measurable deliverables; instead, it focuses on creating lasting behavioral change.

- To improve business processes, you can use the Six Sigma DMAIC process, which stands for the phases in the project methodology: **Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, Control**. To create new processes or products, you can use the Six Sigma DMADV process: **Define, Measure, Analyze, Design, Verify**.
- PRINCE2 (**PR**ojects **IN** **C**ontrolled **E**nvironments) is a project management methodology and certification that aims to equip project managers with knowledge of best practices and processes. Unlike the PMP certification, it doesn't require a number of prerequisites.
- Rapid application development (RAD) is a type of agile project management methodology that aims to facilitate faster software development.

Organizational structure:

- Organizational structure refers to the way a company or organization is arranged or structured. This structure also tells you how job tasks are divided and coordinated and how all the different members of the organization relate to one another.
- organization's structure is most commonly mapped out using a reporting chart or "org chart," which is short for "organizational chart." Reporting charts show the relationship between people and groups within the organization, and details who each person or group reports to. And how job tasks are divided between the employees.
- There are a few different types of organizational structures:
 - o Classic
 - o matrix
- The Classic grouping includes what are usually called "functional" or "top-down" structures. it follows a typical chain of command where the Chief Executive Officer, and other executives are at the top, followed by directors or managers, then their direct reports and so on. Where employees are grouped according to the functions of their role.
- You might think of a Matrix structure as a grid where you still have people above you, but you also have people in adjacent departments who expect to hear updates on your work progress.
- the Classic structure follows a traditional, top-down system of reporting, and the Matrix structure has direct higher-ups to report to and stakeholders from other departments or programs.
- If you are a project manager in a classical type of structure, you may need to consult with functional managers to understand your resources and the capacity of each teammate, as well as to familiarize yourself with each function's internal processes and approval structure. Your authority may be slightly limited due to competing priorities, approval chains, and other complexities, but setting expectations up front will enable you to navigate the organization and execute your project successfully.
- The **Matrix** structure differs from the Classic structure in that the employees have two or more managers. Functional areas tend to cross paths more frequently, and depending on the nature of the work, the responsible manager for each area has the most authority.
- For example an engineering matrix organization:

- the most usual reason for failure of the matrix results from either foot-dragging or downright sabotage on the part of functional management and even by lower level supervision.
- If everyone involved in the matrix is “a believer,” and every effort is expended to make it work, the matrix will work and will result in outstanding project accomplishment
- The matrix organization has many advantages which far outweigh its principal disadvantage of complexity. Among the more universally accepted advantages of the matrix which go beyond the advantages of project management in general are the following:
 - o *Project Objectives Clear.*
 - o *Project Integration*
 - o *Efficient Use of Resources*
 - o *Information Flow*
 - o *Retention of Disciplinary Teams*
 - o *High Morale*
 - o *Development of Project Managers*
 - o *Project Shutdown*
- One way organizational structure can impact the way you manage a project is by the amount of authority given to the project manager. And another is through resource availability.
- *In a classic structured organization, you may have less authority and tighter scope looking for approvals from managers for tasks and resources. While in matrix organizations you may have limited resources and negotiate priority for tasks with other manager of the team members because a single employee could have multiple managers and be working on many projects and the same time*
- Because there isn't always a clear chain of command in a Matrix structure, you need to make sure you have identified and communicated with anyone you might need to report to and get approval from well before the project begins.

The role of a project management office:

- Project Management Office, or PMO, is a group within an organization that defines, sets, and helps maintain project management standards and processes throughout that organization. And project managers could work inside the PMO or even outside of it in other departments.
- Functions of a PMO:
 - o **Strategic planning and governance:** most important function. This involves defining project criteria, selecting projects according to the organization’s business goals.

- **Best practices:** help implement best practices and processes within their organization. They also share lessons learned from previous successful projects.
- **Common project culture:** help set common project culture practices, This helps keep project management practices consistent and efficient across the entire organization.
- **Resource management:** responsible for managing and allocating people and equipment, PMOs help define the roles and responsibilities needed on any given project. PMOs provide training, mentoring, and coaching to all employees, but project managers in particular.
- **Creation of project documentation, archives, and tools:** invest in and provide templates, tools, and software to help manage projects. Once a project closes, they archive all of the documents created during the project for future reference and to capture lessons learned.
- A googler says: "My role specifically in working in a PMO is ensuring that we're connecting all of the different parts that are associated with projects to ensure that they are all connected together".
- A googler says "One of the most critical things that Project Managers get to do is they get to have a bird's eye view of everything that's happening in a project".
- A googler talking about different stages of her career: "at each stage of these I have loved every piece of it."

Organization's culture:

- The culture may include: things like languages, food, clothing, and types of dress, and also beliefs, traditions, and customs. organization's culture provides context and acts as a guide for what their people value, how they operate on a daily basis, how they relate to one another, and how they can be expected to perform. In other words, organizational culture can be thought of as the company's personality.
- Understanding the organization's culture helps during planning and building a team or motivating them, also help minimize conflict.
- The organization's mission and values can provide clues about its culture.
- Demonstrating how the project supports the organization's mission or aligns with its values, help you get approvals and resources.
- Does the management team care about speed over perfection? How do people within the organization make decisions? Do they thoroughly examine every option for every decision? This will help inform which values are the most important to them and how you can approach your decision-making.
- Ideally, you'll want to have a good sense of an organization's culture before you start the first phase of your project.
- To help you gain a better sense of an organization's culture, consider the following questions. How do people prefer to communicate? Is it primarily through scheduled meetings, via email, over the phone? How are decisions made, majority vote or top down approvals? What kinds of rituals are in place when someone new comes to the office? Are they taken out to lunch, given a tour of the building or introduced to the staff? How are projects typically run? Do they prefer a Classic, do they prefer Matrix, or some other style of project management? And finally, what

- kinds of practices, behaviors, and values are reflected by the people in the organization? Is overtime or weekend work an expectation? Are there company sanctioned social events?
- it's important to understand your impact. Be aware of your role as a change agent. A change agent is someone who helps the organization transform by focusing on improving organizational effectiveness and development.
 - quote from Peter Drucker, an expert on management: "Culture eats strategy for breakfast." Drucker is implying that the culture of a company always influences its success, regardless of how effective the company's business model may be.
 - Long story short, an organization culture may be important because of the following:
 - Identity: means An organization's culture defines its identity. Its identity essentially describes the way the company conducts business, both internally and externally.
 - People: Strong, positive organizational culture helps retain a company's best employees.
 - Processes: an organization culture has a direct impact on it's processes and ultimately it's productivity, such as how important feedback is, and how much opportunities the employees are given to comment.
 - Before accepting a position you might want to ask questions about:
 - **Atmosphere**
 - What is the company's dress code?
 - How do people typically share credit at this company?
 - Is risk-taking encouraged, and what happens when people fail?
 - How do managers support and motivate their team?
 - How do people in this role interact with customers and users?
 - When and how do team members give feedback to one another?
 - What are some workplace traditions?
 - What are some of the ways the company celebrates success?
 - **Policies**
 - What are the policies around sick days and vacation?
 - Does the company allow for employee flexibility (e.g., working from home, flexible working hours)?
 - What policies are in place that support employees sharing their identity in the workplace?
 - **Processes**
 - What is the company's onboarding process?
 - How do employees measure the impact of their work?
 - **Values**
 - What are the company's mission and value statements?
 - How might the person in this role contribute to the organization's mission?
 - How does the organization support professional development and career growth?
 - **Listen to people's stories**
 - What were employees' experiences with similar projects in the past?
 - What can they tell you about key stakeholders and customers?
 - **Take note of company rituals**
 - How are birthdays and holidays celebrated?

- Do employees generally eat lunch at the same time and in the same place?
- Watch employee interactions: Observing how employees interact can help you tailor your interaction style to the company norm.
- Are employee interactions more formal or informal in nature?
- Are ideas solicited from employees in different roles?
- **Understand your impact**
- **Sharpen your communication skills**
- Mentors told a googler: " when you're coming to work every day, ask what are the top three challenges that you want to solve today?"
- Examples about organization's cultures:
 - The Family Java coffeehouse: The company has invested in a relationship-driven, employees-first approach. This helps foster a warm, comfortable, and calm environment for both employees and customers alike. Because The Family Java's organizational culture has cultivated employees who genuinely care about the company and their jobs, those employees create the same environment for their customers to enjoy.
 - The Family Java is able to capitalize on the critical link between culture and strategic goals to achieve optimal performance.

Change management:

- If you are launching a new product in the organization, understanding the organization's structure and culture will also help you get people to adopt the new product and change to use it instead of the old one. Because success of the project depends on people adopting it.
- Implementing a new project can mean changes to processes, budgets, schedules, and employee roles and responsibilities. Even aesthetic changes, like building a new wing, renovating the lobby, or switching to a new company logo, means employees will have to adjust to something new and different.
- As a project manager you may not be fully responsible for change management
- Feel free to read through additional resources from other organizations to learn more.
- Change management in project management is centered around three core concepts:
 - The first core concept is creating a sense of ownership and urgency around the project.
 - Ownership means getting others to feel they are empowered to take responsibility for the successful completion of their tasks.
 - Urgency means getting them to understand that the project is important and to identify what actions need to be taken to move the project along.
 - figure out the right combination of skills and personalities when selecting the people who will work on your team.
 - The final core concept is the ever important one, effective communication.
- many of the principles of Agile Project Management align with successful change management.
- The project manager may not be the one responsible for the change management, or may be partially responsible. Now when thinking about change management related to your project start by asking the following questions:
 - How will the organization react to change?
 - Which influencers can affect change?
 - What are the best means of communication?

- What change management practices will lead to the successful implementation of my project?
- Best practices in change management:
 - Be proactive: Proactive and inclusive change management planning can help keep any potentially impacted stakeholders aware of the upcoming changes.
 - **Communicate about upcoming changes:** Communication should occur regularly among impacted stakeholders, the change management team, and the project team.
 - **Follow a consistent process:** The change management process should be established and documented early on in your project to guide how the project will handle change. Also the organization may have a change plan that include: when the promotion of the change should happen, when training should occur, when the launch or release will occur, and corresponding steps for each phase of the process.
 - **Practice empathy:** Changes are inevitable, but we are often resistant to them. By being empathetic to the challenges and anxiety change can bring, you can support the process in subtle ways.
 - **Use tools:** such as:
 - **Feedback mechanisms:** such as surveys.
 - Flowcharts: can visualize the project's development process.
 - Culture mapping: can illustrate the company's culture and how the company's values, norms, and employees behavior may be affected by the change.

- the C-Suite in an organization is the chiefs level officers of an organization.

Governance in business is the management framework within which decisions are made and accountability and responsibility are determined. In simple terms, governance is understanding who is in charge.

- Each organization is governed by its own set of standards and practices that direct and control its actions. Those standards and practices are called **corporate governance**.
- **steering committees.** Steering committees decide on the priorities of an organization and manage the general course of its operations.
- Project governance is the framework for how project decisions are made. This includes:
 - Considering the long- and short-term interests of your organization
 - Making thoughtful decisions about which projects to take on and avoiding projects if you do not have sufficient resources
 - Providing timely, relevant, and reliable information to the board of directors and other major stakeholders
 - Eliciting the input and buy-in of senior managers since they are the decision-makers
 - During the initiation phase, prioritizing clear, reachable, and sustainable goals in order to reduce confusion and conflict
 - During the planning phase, assigning ownership and accountability to an experienced team to deliver, monitor, and control the process
 - During the execution phase, learning from mistakes and adapting to new or improved knowledge
- corporate governance can help support project governance, as it provides oversight on compliance and mitigating risk and offers guidance and direction for project managers.

Fundamentals of project initiation

- Initiation begins after a problem or opportunity has been identified within an organization. Often, stakeholders like senior leaders at a company will initiate a project to address a specific need for the business
- It's your responsibility as the project manager to help identify the project goals, resources, and other details based on initial discussions with the project stakeholders. Even though someone else might come up with an idea for the project, it's still your job to figure out all the important pieces that need to come together in order to get the work done.
- The initiation phase is a crucial time for asking stakeholders the right questions, performing research, determining resources, and clearly documenting the key components of a project.
- Cost benefit analysis: is the process of adding up the expected value of a project—the benefits—and comparing them to the dollar costs.
- To do a cost benefit analysis, you may discuss the project with the stakeholders, and ask some question to find the benefits:
 - o What value will this project create?
 - o How much money could this project save our organization?
 - o How much money will it bring in from existing customers?
 - o How much time will be saved?
 - o How will the user experience be improved?

And to determine the costs:

- o How much time will people have to spend on this project?
 - o What will be the one-time costs?
 - o Are there any ongoing costs?
 - o What about long-term costs?
- Taking into consideration the benefit the project will bring to the customers, tell how the project will benefit the stakeholders which affects the success of the project.
- Key components of initiation:
 - o Goals: the goal is what you've been asked to do and what you're trying to achieve.
 - o Scope: the process to define the work that needs to happen to complete the project.
 - o Deliverables: the products and services that you will create for your customer, client or project sponsor. can be tangible or intangible.
 - o success criteria: the standards by which you measure how successful a project was in reaching its goals.
 - o Stakeholders: Stakeholders are key to making informed decisions at every step of the project, including the initiation phase.
 - o Resources: generally refer to the budget, people, materials, and other items that you will have at your disposal.
- Project charters: clearly define the project and its goals and outline what is needed to accomplish them.
- When setting the project's goals and meeting with the stakeholders a googler says: " When I'm trying to set the goals of a project, I apply very in depth, active listening."

- Also that googler said:” Someone taught me recently the value of building that "listening to learn" muscle.”

Cost benefit analysis:

- A cost-benefit analysis can minimize risks and maximize gains for projects and organizations.
- It can help you communicate clearly with stakeholders and executives and keep your project on track.
- In addition to the questions above you might also ask questions about intangible benefits such as:
 - o **Customer satisfaction.** Will the project increase customer retention, causing them to spend more on the company’s products or services?
 - o **Employee satisfaction.** Is the project likely to improve employee morale, reducing turnover?
 - o **Employee productivity.** Will the project reduce employee’s overtime hours, saving the company money?
 - o **Brand perception.** Is the project likely to improve the company’s brand perception and recognition, attracting more customers or providing a competitive advantage?
- The process of calculating costs and benefits is also called calculating **return on investment**, or **ROI**.
- One common ROI formula is:

$$(G - C) \div C = ROI$$

-
- In this formula, **G** represents the financial gains you expect from the project, and **C** represents the upfront and ongoing costs of your investment in the project.
- Cost-benefit analysis is an important concept from a PMP exam point of view. Make sure you fully understand it.

Initiation phase components:

- **Project goal:** is the desired outcome of the project. It's what you've been asked to do and what you're trying to achieve.
- A project goal is a clear picture of what you're trying to accomplish, how you're going to accomplish it, and how you know when it has been accomplished.
- A good goal is well defined and detailed.
- make sure that before you start your project, you, your stakeholders, and your team are all clear on the project goals so that you know you're making the right kind of progress.
- **Project deliverables:** are the products or services that are created for the customer, client, or project sponsor.
- Deliverables help project managers, team members, and stakeholders quantify and realize the impact of the project.

- a deliverable is what gets produced or presented at the end of a task, event, or process.
- Take the goal to improve customer response time. the deliverable for that goal could be the creation of email templates
- After defining the goals, you need to make a stakeholder analysis and power grid assess the stakeholder power, which will help you decide how best—and how often—to communicate with team members, investors, and more. Assign roles and responsibilities to promote the service. Create a project charter.

SMART goals: means: specific, measurable, attainable, relevant and time-bounded.

- Specific goals should answer at least two of the questions .
 - What do I want to accomplish?
 - Why is this a goal?
 - Does it have a specific reason, purpose, or benefit?
 - Who is involved? Who is the recipient? Employees, customers, the community at large?
 - Where should the goal be delivered?
 - Finally, to what degree?
 - In other words, what are the requirements and constraints?
- Measurable goals: meaning we can determine that they were objectively met. and also, a tool to help people stay motivated. You can tell the goal is measurable by asking how much, how many, and how will I know when it's accomplished? And you can measure goals with metrics and benchmarks.
- Attainable goals: Can it reasonably be reached based on the metrics? figure out if your goal is attainable, ask: how can it be accomplished? Break down the goal into smaller parts and see if it makes sense.
- Relevant goal: first ask does it make sense to try and reach this goal? how the goal lines up with other goals, priorities and values. Ask whether the goal seems worthwhile. Does the effort involved balance out the benefits? Does it match your organizations' other needs and priorities? There might be a budget to complete the project now, but will the company be able to sustain the project over time? Is there an audience that will continue to use the product or service once it's delivered?
- Time-bound: means your goal has a deadline.

work smarter, not harder.

- example, your **specific** goal is to attain a Google Career Certificate. You can make this goal **attainable** by deciding that you will complete one course per month. This goal is **relevant** because it supports your desire to make a career change. Finally, you can make this goal **time-bound** by deciding that you will complete the program within six months. After defining each of these components, your SMART goal then becomes: Obtain a Google Career Certificate by taking one course per month within the next six months.

Peer graded assignment:

- The rubric is a checklist of items your assignment must include. Each item is worth a certain number of points. You can review a rubric to understand how your assignment will be graded and to grade others' work.

Objectives and key results (OKR):

- OKRs help establish and clarify goals or objectives for an organization, department, project or person.
- OKRs take SMART goals a step further by combining a goal and more detailed metrics to determine a measurable outcome.
- OKR is an acronym for objectives and key results. Objectives define what needs to be achieved and describe a desired outcome. Key results define how the project team knows whether or not they have met their objective.
- Organizations often set OKRs at different levels, such as the company level, department or team level, and project level.
- Company level OKRs are commonly shared across an organization so that everyone is clear on the company's goals. They are usually updated on an annual basis to help drive the organization in the direction it wants to go.
- Project level OKRs supports and aligns with company OKRs.
- In other words:

Objectives	Key results
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defines what needs to be achieved • Describes a desired outcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The measurable outcomes that objectively define when the objective has been met

- Strong **objectives** meet the following criteria. They are:
 - Aspirational
 - Aligned with organizational goals
 - Action-oriented
 - Concrete
 - Significant
- To help shape each objective, ask yourself and your team:
 - Does the objective help in achieving the project's overall goals?
 - Does the objective align with company and departmental OKRs?
 - Is the objective inspiring and motivational?
 - Will achieving the objective make a significant impact?
- Strong **key results** meet the following criteria:
 - Results-oriented—**not** a task
 - Measurable and verifiable
 - Specific and time-bound
 - Aggressive yet realistic
- To help shape your key results, ask yourself and your team the following:
 - What does success mean?
 - What metrics would prove that we've successfully achieved the objective?

The project scope:

- It's defined as the project's boundaries, and at google "an agreed upon understanding as to what is included or excluded from a project."
- The scope outlines: the project definition and who it will be delivered to and who will be using the end result of the project, also the project's complexity, Scope also includes the project timeline, budget, and resources.
- Some questions to help you determine the scope:
 - o Where did the project come from?
 - o Why is it needed? What is
 - o the project expected to achieve?
 - o What does the project sponsor have in mind?
 - o Who approves the final results?
- defining project scope should happen during the initial planning stage.

Project Scope Definition	
Stakeholders	How did you arrive at the decision to update the dining space? Did the request originate from the restaurant owner, customers, or other stakeholders? Who will approve the scope for the project?
Goals	What is the reason for updating the dining space? What isn't working in the current dining space? What is the end goal of this project?
Deliverables	Which dining space is being updated? What exactly needs to be updated? Does the dining space need a remodel?
Resources	What materials, equipment, and people will be needed? Will we need to hire any contractors? Will we need to obtain a floor plan and building permits?
Budget	What is the budget for this project? Is it fixed or flexible?
Schedule	How much time do we have to complete the project? When does the project need to be completed?
Flexibility	How much flexibility is there? What is the highest priority: hitting the deadline, sticking to the budget, or making sure the result meets all the quality targets?

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- Scope creep: Changes, growth, and uncontrolled factors that affect a project scope at any point after the project begins, scope creep sources are two:
 - o External: might come from the customer, business strategy shift, technology change.
 - Some useful tips to deal with external scope creep:
 - make sure the stakeholders have visibility into the project.
 - get clarity on the requirements and ask for constructive criticism of the initial product proposal.

- set ground rules and expectations for stakeholder involvement once the project gets started.
 - come up with a plan for how to deal with out-of-scope requests.
 - be sure to get these agreements and plans in writing.
 - ★ One of the leading causes of external scope creep is not being clear on the requirements before defining the scope.
 - Internal: it comes from a project team member, a developer.
 - Process changes.
 - Product improvement.
- some best practices for scope management and controlling scope creep:
 - **Define your project's requirements:** communicate with stakeholders to find their exact requirements and document them.
 - **Set a clear project schedule:** Your schedule should outline all of your project's requirements and the tasks that are necessary to achieve them.
 - **Determine what is out of scope:** Make sure your stakeholders, customers, and project team understand when proposed changes are out of scope. And document their potential impact to the project.
 - **Provide alternatives:** Suggest alternative solutions to your customer or stakeholder. Perform a cost-benefit analysis if necessary.
 - **Set up a change control process:** some changes are inevitable, Determine the process for how each change will be defined, reviewed, and approved (or rejected), Make sure your project team is aware of this process.
 - **Learn how to say no:** Sometimes you will have to say no to proposed changes. explain how they will interfere with the budget, timeline, and/or resources defined in your initial project requirements.
 - **Collect costs for out-of-scope work:** If out-of-scope work is required, be sure to document all costs incurred. Be sure to indicate what the charges are for.
- Any time a team member takes on an unplanned task, more is lost than just the time spent working on that task.

The triple constraint model: is the combination of the three most significant restrictions of any project: scope, time, and cost. you can't change one without having an impact on the others.

- Time refers to the project schedule and deadlines. Cost includes the budget, and it also covers resources and the people who will work on the project.
- If the product must look or function in a certain way, then the requirements are a priority, and you could justify changes in cost or time in order to meet the scope requirements.
- In this model it goes as follows: one of them is constant, the second increases and the third will decrease.
- project launch: delivering the final result of the project to the user or client.
- Landing: is measuring the success of your project using the success criteria established at the outset of the project.
- landings are what we strive for and what we celebrate. They are the ultimate reward for all of our efforts.
- After launching the project, you need to check periodically for five years to make sure the project lands otherwise the project won't be counted as a true success.

Success criteria:

- Tells you whether or not the project as a whole was successful.
- They are the specific details of your goals and deliverables that tell you whether you've accomplished what you set out to do.
- They are the standards by which the project will be judged once it's been delivered to stakeholders and customers.
- How to determine project success:
 - measure to determine your project success in a similar way to measuring a goal.
 - get clarity from stakeholders on the project requirements and expectations. You can ask questions and document them:
 - Who ultimately says whether or not the project is successful?
 - What criteria will be measured to determine success?
 - What's the success of this project based on?
 - Use metrics:

- "happiness metrics" measure user attitudes and satisfaction, or perceived ease of use, and you can measure these through surveys.
 - Adoption metrics refers to how the customer uses and adopts a product or service without any issues.
 - Engagement metrics: refers to how often or meaningful customer interaction and participation is over time.
- along with each success criteria on your list, to also include the methods for how success will be measured, how often it's measured, and who's responsible for measuring it.
 - Customers and stakeholders are the ones going to judge if the project was a success.

Sometimes when a project manager works on a project there is many stakeholders, each one with a different interpretation of the project fundamentals and the PM has to satisfy and work with them all and to do that, break it down to the following:

1. Understand – What is the position each stakeholder has? And why they have it? Is it logical or emotional.
2. Assess – How does that position compare with the organizational view of the project? And according to that determine the weight of the stakeholder.
3. Adapt – Adjust elements of the project to manage any variance between views and perspectives. on many occasions, all that is required is an adjustment to how you communicate to those stakeholders.

Reasons for this different interpretation to exist:

For fresh PMs because they don't have established relationships with the project stakeholders, they don't have a sense of the natural bias, approach, etc. that each of those stakeholders have. The new PM likely also doesn't understand the inevitable political environment that sits below the surface and impacts some stakeholder actions. also lack the experience to confidently balance conflicting perspectives from different stakeholders.

stakeholders will always find new and innovative ways to frustrate you. Sometimes it's deliberate, often it isn't; but they will always be one of the most challenging aspects of project delivery.

Using OKRs to evaluate progress:

- Communicating and tracking OKRs: it's important to communicate them to your team, assign an owner to every key result so that everybody knows who's responsible for what.
- Measuring progress: Determine how you will score your OKRs maybe percentage, milestones, or scale 1-10, At Google, OKRs are usually graded on a scale of 0.0 to 1.0, with 1.0 meaning the objective was fully achieved. Each individual key result is graded and then the grades are averaged to determine the score for that OKR. **Set your scoring expectations**, Google's 0.0–1.0 scale, the expectation is to set ambitious OKRs and aim to achieve an average of at least 0.6 to 0.7 across all OKRs, scoring lower may mean the team is not achieving what it could be. Scoring higher may mean the aspirational goals are not being set high enough. **Schedule checkpoints** it can be helpful to have monthly check-ins on the progress of OKRs you'll grade each of your OKRs to evaluate how well the team did to achieve its goals.

Stakeholders:

- people who are interested in and affected by the project's completion and success.
- ★ Accessibility: for a googler it means: "actively removing any barriers that might prevent persons with disabilities from being able to access technology, information, or experiences, and leveling in the playing field so everyone has an equal chance of enjoying life and being successful."
- **Choosing the team:**
 - a project manager will make a list of roles that they'll need on their team to complete each task.
 - the project manager decides how many people they'll need on their team. It could be three or four and sometimes it could be hundreds. Too many may mean bad communication and too few could mean short on deliverables.
 - project manager needs to ensure that everyone on the team has the right skills to do the job. Looking at technical skills and soft skills too.
 - project manager also has to factor in each person's availability. you need to value diversity early on when building your team. Diversity is best leveraged when it is acknowledged and highlighted as an asset.
 - whether each person will feel motivated to complete their assigned tasks. A pre-assigned member not necessarily not motivated, and a volunteer is probably extra motivated.
- Sometimes team members need to adapt and take on more than one role at a time. This usually happens if the company is small or resources are limited.
- we always have these project roles. Project sponsors, team members, customers or users, stakeholders, and of course, the project manager.
 - Project sponsor: is the person who is accountable for the project and who ensures the project delivers the agreed upon value to the business.
 - Team members: are the heart of the operation. They're the people doing the day-to-day work and making the project happen.
 - The customers: are the people who will get some sort of value from a successfully landed project. You can think of them as the buyers of the project. Such as an organization
 - users are the people that ultimately use the product that your project will produce. Such as the employees of the customer organization.
 - Stakeholders: are anyone involved in the project; those who have a vested interest in the project's success.
 - Primary stakeholders are people who expect to benefit directly from the project's completion,
 - while secondary stakeholders play an intermediary role and are indirectly impacted by the project. Secondary stakeholders may be contractors or members of a partner organization.
 - project manager: the person who plans, organizes and oversees the whole project.
- A googler says: "The most important part about program management is understanding the personalities of the people you work with so that you can tailor your approach to make sure

that you're working effectively with them. Think about it this way. You might be working with an introverted person. That person needs different types of attention than an extroverted person.”

Stakeholder analysis:

- is a visual representation of all the stakeholders. It helps you avoid surprises, build necessary partnerships, and ensure you're involving the right people at the right time.
- There are three key steps to kicking off a stakeholder analysis:
 - o make a list of all the stakeholders that the project impacts.
 - o Then determine the level of interest and influence for each stakeholder. The higher these two are the more important the stakeholder is.
 - o assess their ability to participate, and find ways to involve them. By knowing their motivations and inspirations. This takes time, interpersonal skills, and insight into the organization's internal political workings.
- Influence: measures how much power a stakeholder has and how much the stakeholder's actions affect the project outcome.
- Interest: How much are the needs of the stakeholder affected by the project operations and outcomes.
- You could act as the following power grid with the stakeholders according to influence and interest.

- You may create a steering committee made up of a high influence and high interest stakeholders. These people will be the most senior decision-making body on any project. The PMs are responsible for bringing the right project information to the steering committee so that decisions can be quickly made.
- Stakeholder buy-in is the process of involving these people in decision-making to hopefully reach a broader consensus on the organization's future.
- Tips for gaining key stakeholder buy-in include:
 - o Clearly mapping the work of the project to the goals of the stakeholder.
 - o Describing how the project aligns with the goals of the stakeholder's department or team.

- Listening to feedback from the stakeholder and finding ways to incorporate their feedback into the project's charter where appropriate.
- Suggested questions for stakeholders
 - What are your most important priorities/goals?
 - How will this initiative/project support you and your most important priorities?
 - What role would you like to play within this initiative/project?
 - Here's how I plan to keep people informed; does that work for you?
 - What can I clarify for you?
 - What are your expectations? What would you like for the project to accomplish?
 - What would success look like for you?
 - Who else do you recommend I reach out to about this initiative?
 - What information or insights do you have that might be challenging for me to find?
 - Where do you see me getting support for this initiative? Facing resistance?
 - What additional thoughts/questions do you have?
- Keep in mind that investors are less interested in what is happening in the project than customers but they have more influence with their finance.
- **RACI:** chart helps to define roles and responsibilities for individuals or teams to ensure work gets done efficiently.
- There are four types of participation included in a RACI chart:
 - Responsible: refers to those doing the work to complete the task.
 - Accountable: refers to those making sure the work gets done.
 - Consulted: includes those giving feedback, like subject matter experts or decision-makers.
 - informed, which includes those just needing to know the final decisions or that a task is complete.

R: Responsible	Assigned to complete the task or deliverable			
A: Accountable	Has final decision-making authority and accountability for completion (only one per task)			
C: Consulted	Must be consulted before a decision or action is taken			
I: Informed	Must be informed after a decision or action is taken			
Task	List Roles			
	R	A	C	I
Task 1				
Task 2				
Task 3				
Task 4				

- Write the roles or people's names in a row across the top of your chart:-
- ★ Pro-tip: use roles rather than names if some people might take on more than one role.
- there will never be more than one person designated as "accountable."
- At least one responsible for each task.
- There might be some confusion, that could be resolved by RACI chart such as:
 - there might be unbalanced workloads
 - there could be an unclear hierarchy.

- unclear ownership of decisions
- overlapping work.
- excessive communication.
- While communication is usually a good thing, too much communication can actually make things more complicated. It can cause information overload.
- Workload unbalance known as creating **silos**, where the knowledge and responsibility for a task falls on one person.
- Balancing the workload isn't always healthy to your team this isn't always healthy for the project or your team. If you find that you don't have the right people to assign responsibilities to, take a step back and evaluate your team.
- When creating a RACI chart, put down all the accountabilities and responsibilities then look up the consultations and information because not every task must have a consultant or an informant.
- For some reasons project may fail even after you do your best to make them work, some of these reasons are:
 - **Unclear expectations:** such as the end goal, schedule or budget.
 - **Unrealistic expectations:** like setting a short time frame for a complicated task. Which will likely result in quality issues.
 - **Miscommunication:** to avoid that use charts and Set expectations for your communication approach early.
 - **Lack of resources:** without proper planning and documenting the resources could be over-tasked such as budget, team members, or materials.
 - **Scope creep.**
- **Resources:**
 - Budget
 - People
 - Materials
- **Budget:** is an estimate of the amount of money a project will cost to complete. You need it to buy materials, hire vendors or do marketing. Also account for taxes and extra fees.
- **People:** such as the project manager, or the marketing manager, or people outside of your company who have unique skills and can do certain tasks that people in your organization can't do personally.
- **Materials:** These are items you need to help get the project done. Such as the lumber for a construction project. Or computers and software for IT projects.
- Now to organize your resources you need tools:
 - Tools are aids that make it easier for a project manager or team to manage resources and organize work.
 - Tools can help you to:
 - track tasks
 - manage budgets
 - collaborate with teammates.

Documentation:

- Clear and consistent documentation can ensure transparency and clear communication
- Documentations answers key questions such as:
 - what problem are you trying to solve?
 - What are the project goals?
 - What are the scope and deliverables, and who are the project's stakeholders?
 - what resources does the team need to complete their work?
- Documentation also helps preserve decisions made early on in the project and can serve as a reference point for team members who might join later in the project life cycle.
- formal documentation, like an e-mail, a presentation, or a digital document.
- documenting decisions can help you uncover tasks, timelines, or costs you hadn't previously considered.
- Two common types of project documentation:
 - the project proposal: a form of documentation that comes at the very beginning of the project. its purpose is to persuade stakeholders that a project should begin. Typically, a senior organizational leader creates it, A proposal may be a formal document, a presentation, or even a simple email.
 - the project charter: a formal document that clearly defines the project and outlines the necessary details to reach its goals. A project charter helps you get organized, set up a framework for what needs to be done, and communicate those details to others.
- The goals of the above two documentations are as follows:
 - The proposal kicks off the initiation phase by influencing and persuading the company to move forward with the project.
 - The project charter serves a similar purpose and often comes at the end of the initiation phase. a charter will often serve as a point of reference throughout the life of a project. It makes clear that the benefits of the project outweigh the costs.
- Project charter approval means that management is supportive, and it's also a key step to ensure that the project matches the needs of the organization.
- you might ask yourself when performing a cost benefit analysis. That includes questions like:
 - What value will this project create?
 - And how much money could this project save my organization?
 - How much time will people have to spend on this project? You'll include the answers to these questions in your charter.
- creating a project charter is a best practice for ensuring that everyone agrees on how to move forward before entering the planning phase.
- Project charters will vary but usually include some combination of the following key information:
 - introduction/project summary
 - goals/objectives
 - business case/benefits and costs
 - project team
 - scope
 - success criteria
 - major requirements or key deliverables
 - budget

- schedule/timeline or milestones
- constraints and assumptions
- risks
- OKRs
- approvals

Team	Goals/Problem statement	Key success metrics	Target	Achieved
Project sponsor (Name)	The issue(s) we're trying to resolve!	Ex: Cost savings	\$X	\$X
PM (Name)		Ex: Quality improvement	X%	X%
Core project team (Name) (Name) (Name) (Name) (Name)		Ex: Time savings	X%	X%
		Ex: Capability improvement	X%	X%
		Accessibility considerations		
	Business case What are the benefits of this project?			
Timeline		Risks	Key deliverables	OKRs
Project definition		Risk 1	KD 1	OKR 1
Confirm target metrics		Risk 2	KD 2	OKR 2
Design solution		Risk 3	KD 3	OKR 3
Implementation		Risk 4	KD 4	OKR 4
Sustain				

Tools:

- help you track detailed information about all kinds of tasks, and they make it easy to communicate with lots of different people.
- When you choose the right tool for a project:
 - let you know if a task is on schedule or if it's delayed.
 - increase visibility and transparency.
 - manage a budget,
 - build helpful charts and diagrams,
 - manage contracts and licenses
- Two types of tools: (by complexity)
 - straightforward, like digital spreadsheets or documents
 - more sophisticated, like scheduling and work management software.
- Important considerations when introducing a new tool:
 - **Discuss the tool early and often, if possible**
 - **Ask for feedback from key stakeholders**
 - **Involve the key stakeholders in demonstrations as you get closer to making the final decision on the project tracking tool.**
 - **Ensure the tool is fully functional before the team is introduced to it.**
 - **Set up training for the tool as needed before you ask the team to actually use it.**
- ★ plan for a period of transition if you are replacing an existing tool.
- Types of project management tools: (by functionality)

- scheduling and work management software. Like asana and jira you choose according to:
 - the project methodology you're running
 - the number of tasks and people involved
 - Benefits: help you in assigning tasks, also help you visualize your team's progress.
- tools for productivity: such as word processing tools, like Microsoft Word or Google Docs. Which you can use to create: (online shared documents, meeting agendas, status updates, spreadsheets, RACI charts, project plans) or presentations created in tools, like Microsoft PowerPoint, Keynote, or Google Slides can be a great way to package your project in a visual, easily-digestible way.
- Collaboration tools: rely on to work closely with your teammates. Like e-mail and chat
- ★ Productivity and collaboration tools are mainly for smaller projects while scheduling software is for bigger projects.

Asana: a work management platform that helps teams plan and coordinate their work from daily tasks to strategic initiatives.:

- It's great for
 - building project plans,
 - assigning tasks,
 - automating workflows,
 - tracking progress,
 - and communicating with stakeholders.
- you can use Asana to create a log of tasks, like gathering cost estimates from external vendors, and assign a task to people on the team.

Spreadsheets:

- You can use spreadsheets for:
 - creating timelines
 - billing charts
 - managing budgets
 - tracking tasks.
- With spreadsheets, you can easily transform, visualize, and manipulate information.
- Some templates like:
 - project timeline template is useful if you want to track an entire project from conception to close.
 - project tracking template is useful for tracking your project's budget, deliverables, and other data.
 - Gantt chart combines many of the aspects of other types of project management spreadsheets into one. It organizes tasks by day and is useful for showing the relationships between the many moving parts of a project. It's also helpful for managing a project with multiple collaborators. Gantt charts often include conditional formatting that makes cells change color based on how far along the project is so you can immediately determine how much progress you have made on a particular task.

- timeline template is useful for creating a schedule, tracking events, and visualizing the tasks and milestones involved in a project.
- In a project management role interview you may be asked some questions that could be answered with some tools experience, example questions:
 - How do you know if a project is off track?
 - may ask you to discuss the project management tools you are familiar with or have used in the past.
 - How do you execute tasks within your timeline?
- Googler says: ' As a Project Manager, tools are our best friends.'

Project planning: putting it all together

- The project manager gets assigned in the initiation phase.
- In the planning phase PM and other team members will determine the processes and workflows needed to meet your goals and put together ideas about how to make the project a success.
- you might draw from previous project experience, for planning a new project but since every project is different you will probably need new ideas and approaches.
- Benefits of planning:
 - helps you map out the full project.
 - helps you understand the work needed to achieve your goals.
 - helps coordinate efforts and timelines with other teams, contractors, and vendors.
 - it gives you time to identify and prepare for risks that could impact your project. also gives you the chance to brainstorm ways to mitigate or address those risks.
- Less obvious benefits of planning:
 - help you get "buy-in" from key members of the project team.
 - demonstrates to stakeholders that the team is taking care to start the project with a detailed plan.
 - teamwork

Launching the planning phase:

- The plan does not have to be perfect because probably there will be changes during the project.
- Three **Big** things have to be worked out during this stage:
 - the schedule.
 - the budget.
 - the risk management plan.
- The schedule: is basically a timeline of the project. It includes the start date, the end date, and the dates for things that will happen in between. And to determine those dates you will use time estimation techniques.
- The budget: will account for the total cost to complete the project. The total cost needs to be broken down to determine how much has to be spent on different elements of the project.
- risk management: means searching for possible problems and planning ahead to mitigate these risks.

- First thing after finishing the initiation phase It's important to schedule a meeting (**kickoff meeting**) that will serve as a formal start to project planning.
- project kickoff meeting is the first meeting in which a project team comes together to ground everyone in a shared vision, gain a shared understanding of the project's goals and scope, and to understand each person's individual roles within the team.
- And the ones invited to the meeting are the team members identified in a RACI chart. also invite your stakeholders and your sponsor to the meeting.
- When the project is small or you are working alone the project charter with few emails could be enough but when the project is big meeting are needed and it's important to get together to establish a shared vision, align on the scope, and build team rapport. It's also an opportunity for teammates to ask questions and offer insights, and it's a great time for you to set expectations with the team about how each person will individually contribute to the project.
- Creating a meeting agenda takes an hour usually.
- And it could be split into the following:
 - o Most meetings start with brief introductions. You can allocate about 10 minutes for everyone in the group to introduce themselves and their roles, and if time allows, share a fun fact to help build team rapport.
 - o Then you'll spend about 5 minutes giving an overview of the background of the project. This covers details like how the project came to be and why the project matters. You'll also use this time to set a shared vision.
 - o spend about 5 minutes sharing the goals and the scope. Make clear what is:
 - in-scope.
 - out-of-scope.
 - the target launch date
 - any important milestones
 - o roles. spend about 5 minutes making sure that everyone is clear on what work they'll be responsible for throughout the duration of the project.
 - o collaboration, how the team will work together on the project. You should spend about 10 minutes on this topic, this is a great time to go over tools
 - like a project plan created in a spreadsheet or work management software tool like Asana.
 - determine how the team will communicate with one another, like through daily email updates, a team chat room, and weekly team check-in meetings.
 - o discuss what comes next, you should spend about 10 minutes setting expectations with your teammates for what's coming up.
 - o it's important to set about 15 minutes for questions from the group.
 - This is your team's chance to gain clarity on any of the topics you've discussed so far.
 - It's also your chance to hear from the team and ensure that the project is benefiting from diversity of thoughts, experiences, and ideas.
- After finishing the agenda send it to the attendees a day or two before the meeting.
- Best practices during the kickoff meeting:

- ask a teammate to take notes on key points you discussed throughout the session and to record each teammate's action items.
- send a follow-up email to the group, summarizing key points and outcomes from the meeting, as well as any action items to the attendees.
- Now some best practices for the whole kickoff meeting process:
 - **Set the right time:** consider time zone differences.
 - **Set the right length:** no more than one hour.
 - **Invite the right people:** The goal is to invite attendees who play a role in the development and execution of the project.
 - **Designate a notetaker:** It is critical that you document any feedback, changes, or questions asked by attendees. If you are leading the meeting, designate someone else to take notes, you can also use tools like Chorus Notetaker, Google Keep, Google Docs, or Microsoft OneNote.
 - **Set the agenda: (check the points above)**
 - **Share the agenda:** Prior to the meeting, share the agenda with attendees via email and identify speakers for each topic.
 - **Stick to the agenda:** As a project manager, it is your job to keep the meeting on track.
 - **Follow up after the meeting:** After the meeting, make sure to send out a meeting summary featuring the meeting notes and any action items.
- A project **milestone** is an important point within the project schedule that indicates progress and usually signifies the completion of a deliverable or phase of the project.
- A project **task** is an activity that needs to be accomplished within a set period of time.
- Milestones and project tasks are interconnected. Tasks ladder up to milestones, which are crucial for project tracking.
- The importance of milestones:
 - setting milestones gives you a clear understanding of the amount of work your project will require.
 - they can help keep your project on track.
 - they help you uncover areas where you might need to adjust scope, timelines, or resources to meet your goals.
 - reaching milestones can seriously motivate your team and illustrate real progress to your stakeholders.
 - serve as a great check-in point to highlight your progress to stakeholders.
 - milestones must be completed on time and in sequential order
 - If the team misses the mark to complete a deliverable tied to a specific milestone, it could set back your project schedule,
 - When you set milestones, you assign clear deadlines for certain project deliverables.
-
- How to set a mile stone:
 - evaluate your project as a whole.
 - make a list of what your team needs to do to achieve that goal.
 - The big items that indicate progress are your milestones.
 - some projects might have many milestones, while others might just have two or three.
 - assign each one a deadline.

- you can connect with teammates to discuss the tasks required to reach each milestone and get their estimates for how long these tasks will take.
 - When you set deadlines for milestones, you will also want to consider the needs of your stakeholders.
- There is two ways to help set tasks and milestones:
 - **Top-down scheduling:** lay out the higher-level milestones, then works to break down the effort into project tasks.
 - **Bottom-up scheduling:** the project manager looks at all of the individual tasks that need to be completed and then rolls those tasks into manageable chunks that lead to a milestone.
 - Milestones serve as check-in points along your project to make sure that you are headed in the right direction toward the end goal. Milestones also make projects more manageable.
 - **Milestone-setting pitfalls:**
 - **don't set too many milestones:** When there are too many milestones, their importance is downplayed.
 - **Don't mistake tasks for milestones:** Remember that milestones should represent moments in time, so you need to assign smaller tasks to each milestone.
 - **Don't list your milestones and tasks separately:** Make sure that tasks and milestones can be visualized together in one place, such as a project plan.
 - **Work breakdown structure (WBS):** is a tool that sorts the milestones and tasks of a project in a hierarchy, in the order they need to be completed.
 - Big projects seem a lot less daunting when the work required to get there is broken down step-by-step with a clear pathway from the beginning of the project to the end.
 - One way to create (WBS): tree diagram of project tasks.
 - creating a (WBS) is a helpful exercise for visualizing the tasks of the project,
 - WBSs do not get included in an official project plan instead, they get turned into spreadsheets or work management software.
 - After turning the WBS into spreadsheet:
 - you should have a set of discrete project tasks that ladder up to each of your milestones.
 - you're now in a good position to assign those tasks to members of the project team.
 - How to assign tasks:
 - Tasks are typically assigned according to a person's role in the project.
 - To assign tasks between two or more team members with the same roles, you might take into consideration each person's familiarity with the tasks at hand.
 - consider each teammate's workload.
 - you will ensure that your teammates are clear on their assigned tasks.
 - One benefit of assigning tasks that it creates a sense of personal responsibility for members of the team.
 - Steps to build a WBS:

- **Start with the high-level, overarching project picture. Brainstorm with your team to list the major deliverables and milestones**
- **Identify the tasks that need to be performed in order to meet those milestones**
- **Examine those tasks and break them down further into sub-tasks**
- ★ You can say that: milestones are deliverables and outcomes while tasks are actions.
- Benefits of WBS:
 - Estimate the cost of a project.
 - Establish dependencies
 - Determine the project timeline and develop a schedule.
 - Write a statement of work (SoW): legal document defines what you need from the vendor your team hires to complete a project milestone (and what they need from you), so everyone knows what's expected.
 - Assign responsibilities and clarify roles.
 - Track the progress of a project.
 - Identify risk.
- Tips for making a WBS:
 - **The 100% rule.** The work represented by your WBS must include 100% of the work necessary to complete the overarching goal.
 - **Mutually exclusive.** Do not include a sub-task twice or account for any amount of work twice.
 - **Outcomes, not actions.** Remember to focus on deliverables and outcomes rather than actions.
 - **The 8/80 rule.** There are several ways to decide when a work package is small enough without being too small. For example a work package should take no less than 8 hours and no more than 80 hours.
 - **Three levels.** Generally speaking, a WBS should include about three levels of detail.
 - **Make assignments.** Every work package should be assigned to a specific team or individual.
- WBS formats:
 - **Outline structure:** A text outline is the simplest WBS format.
 - **Hierarchical structure:** Because it is a table, this format fits easily onto a page.
 - **Tabular view:** A tabular view is a more visually intuitive way to show hierarchy using a table.
 - **WBS dictionary:** A WBS dictionary is formatted like the hierarchical structure, but it includes a brief description of each work package.
- A googler says: " Planning sets a tone for what we're actually doing together. It creates a sense of team."
- **Project plan components:**
 - it helps you document the scope, tasks, milestones, and overall activities of the project.
 - most plans contain these five basic elements. These are:
 - tasks

- milestones
- people
- Documentation
- time.
- Projects plan's components:
 - Schedule: estimate the amount of time it will take to complete the project
 - Scope and goals: will be captured initially in your **project charter**
 - Work Breakdown Structure (WBS): In addition to the WBS, further documentation—such as a RACI chart—will help.
 - Budget: The project budget is often linked to the project plan because it is heavily dependent on key elements of the project.
 - Management plans: such as the change management plan, risk management plan, and communication plan.

Time estimation:

- after identifying and helping assign tasks, estimate how long they'll take to complete.
- Time estimation is a prediction of the total amount of time required to complete a task.
- Effort estimation is a prediction of the amount and difficulty of active work required to complete a task.
- Effort estimation differs from time estimation in that effort quantifies the amount of time it will take a person to complete work on a task. On the flip side, time refers to the overall duration of the task from start to finish. That includes inactive time.
- Time estimation includes work time also idle time while effort estimation includes work time only.
- An unrealistic effort estimate can negatively impact a project schedule. Often, the culprit for under estimating effort is optimism.
- Optimism is a trait of a great project manager and leader but, too much optimism can lead you to overlook potential risks that could set your plans behind schedule.
- Your teammates will have the **most realistic** understanding of the amount of work required to complete a task and should be able to provide you with the best estimate
- **Sub-tasks** are smaller tasks that are required to complete a larger task.
- Asking the teammate assigned to the task for their estimate is likely to yield a more accurate estimation. But you can push back on their estimates as needed.
- A **buffer** is extra time added to the end of a task or a project to account for unexpected slowdowns or delays in work progress. There is two types of buffers:
 - Task buffers: which refer to extra time tacked on to a specific task. Task buffers should be used primarily for tasks that are out of the project team's control. should be used more sparingly for tasks within the project team's control.
 - Project buffers: extra time to the overall project schedule.
- Adding a buffer to every task could lengthen your project schedule unnecessarily,
- In case of having delay in a project there is some practices that might help, such as:
 - sharing it with management (escalate).
 - Work with the team

- **Elimination of tasks:** It is possible that all of the tasks initially listed didn't need to be completed. There may have been unnecessary work added in.
 - **Increased team size:** Kendra could have addressed the potential schedule risk by requesting more resources early on in the project, or shrunk the team by eliminating unnecessary team members.
 - **Streamlining of activities:** There may have been some tasks that could have been done in parallel, or at least not in sequential order.
- **planning fallacy:** describes our tendency to underestimate the amount of time it will take to complete a task, as well as the costs and risks associated with that task, due to **optimism bias**.
- Optimism bias is when a person believes that they are less likely to experience a negative event.
- **Capacity planning:** you'll need it to determine, if you have the right number of people to get the work done.
- Capacity refers to the amount of work that the people or resources assigned to the project can reasonably complete in a set period of time.
- Capacity planning refers to the act of allocating people, and resources to project tasks. And determining whether or not you have the necessary resources required to complete the work on time.
- The **critical path** refers to the list of project milestones that you must reach in order to meet the project goal on schedule. As well as the mandatory tasks that contribute to the completion of each milestone.
- your critical path includes the bare minimum number of tasks and milestones you need to reach your project goal.
- Included in the capacity planning is:
 - The longest path is your critical path
 - you need to be able to identify which task can happen in parallel and identify which task can happen sequentially.
 - Knowing the parallel tasks help you identify efficiencies, while identifying sequential tasks helps you identify the tasks that you need to prioritize early on in the project.
 - You also need to determine which project tasks have a fixed start date.
 - some tasks might have an earliest start date.
 - identify if a task has float, also sometimes known as slack.
- **Float** refers to the amount of time you can wait to begin a task before it impacts the project schedule, and threatens the project outcome. *tasks on the critical path should have zero float*
And tasks that do have float are not a part of the critical path.
- **How to create a critical path**
 - **Capture all tasks:** capture all of the tasks associated with the completion of the effort, remember to use documents such as (WBS)
 - **Set dependencies:** figure out which tasks must be completed before other tasks can start, to figure out dependencies ask:
 - Which task needs to take place before this task?
 - Which task can be finished at the same time as this task?
 - Which task needs to happen right after this task?
 - **Create a network diagram:** These diagrams help visualize:

- The path of the work from the start of the project to the end of the project.
 - Which tasks can be performed in parallel.
 - Which non-essential tasks are NOT on the critical path
 - **Make time estimates:** consult key stakeholders to get accurate time estimates for each task. Time estimates can be reviewed and updated throughout the project, as necessary.
 - **Find the critical path:** to find it only include the tasks that, if they go unfinished, will impact the project's finish date. You can also calculate the critical path using two common approaches: the **forward pass** and the **backward pass**. These techniques are useful if you are asked to identify the **earliest and latest start dates** or the **slack**.
 - The **forward pass** refers to when you start at the beginning of your project task list and add up the duration of the tasks on the critical path to the end of your project.
 - The **backward pass** is the opposite—start with the final task or milestone and move backwards through your schedule to determine the shortest path to completion.
- A **network diagram** often looks like a chart with boxes and arrows and is a graphical representation of project tasks, responsibilities, and workflow.
- **Soft skills** are personal characteristics that help people work effectively with others. These include crucial communication and interpersonal skills. Such as:
 - asking the right questions: asking effective, open-ended questions
 - negotiating effectively. Part of your job is to bridge the gap between high-level goals of the project and the day-to-day perspective of your team. by asking follow-up questions. you can create a sense of shared ownership over the project outcomes.
 - practicing empathy. you might practice empathy by asking each person about their workload also, People like to feel their work is valued, so part of empathy is remembering to always be appreciative of the work, collaboration, and support that you're getting from the team.
 -
- An open-ended question is a question that cannot be answered with a yes or a no. The answer provides the relevant details of what you need to know.
- Empathy refers to a person's ability to relate to the thoughts and feelings of others.
- A googler says: " Having a technical background and having really good people skills is hard to find."
- Also a googler says: " Soft skills to me have a lot to do with emotional intelligence—being able to read other people and then ultimately really knowing yourself—and being able to read the team"
- an anchor of a good project plan is a clear schedule containing all the tasks of a project, their owners, and when they need to be completed.
- A **Gantt chart** is a horizontal bar chart that maps out a project schedule. it's a highly visual representation of a projects tasks with clear breakdowns of who's responsible for the work and when those tasks are due.
- Gantt charts are almost like calendars.

- Creating a Gantt chart in a spreadsheet is pretty simple. You can organize your left columns by items like task title, task owner, start date, due date, duration, and percent of task complete.
- Gantt charts are a useful tool, but they are far from the only option for your project plan

Project plan best practice:

- Ensure careful review of project deliverables, milestones, and tasks
- give yourself time to plan
- recognize and plan for the inevitable (things will go wrong).
- stay curious: ask lots and lots of questions to team mates
- champion your plan: champion it! Tell your team why it benefits them to stay on top of the plan.

Key information to include in a project plan:

- **Task ID numbers or task names**
- **Task durations**
- **Start and finish dates**
- **Who is responsible for what**

As a general rule,:

- it is best to use a spreadsheet for a simple project
- project management software for a more complex project.
- Spreadsheets are an excellent tool to use for project plans, particularly for projects that are less complex and that have a clear assignment of tasks.

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- **Kanban boards** are a visual tool used to manage tasks and workflows. Kanban boards can be created on whiteboards, magnetic boards, poster boards, computer programs, and more. Tasks associated with the project are written on cards. These cards are placed in columns, which represent the progress made.
- Kanban boards are useful for all kinds of projects, they are typically most suitable for project teams working in an **Agile** project management approach.

Purposes of a Kanban board:

- Give a quick visual understanding of work details and provide critical task information.
- Facilitate handoffs between stakeholders
- Help with capturing metrics and improving workflows.

Creating a kanban board:

- it is best practice to gather the necessary information and lay out key elements, such as tasks, status, dates, and durations. That information is useful when building your board.
- Cards will vary in style—you can even use sticky notes on a whiteboard—but most cards will contain a few key details about the task that they represent.
- When creating card for a kanban board (physical cards):
 - o Front:

- **Title and unique identifier:** reference for tasks and ID numbers.
- **Description of work:** Briefly describe the task to be accomplished.
- **Estimation of effort:** Estimate the amount of work it will take to complete the task.
- **Who is assigned to the task:** Indicate who is responsible for completing the task.
- Back:
 - **Start date:** Include the start date of the task.
 - **Blocked days:** Indicate which days your task may be halted.
 - **Finish date:** As with any plan, it is important to track when the task is supposed to be finished.

Project budget: is the estimated monetary resources needed to achieve the project's goals and objectives.

- You break the budget down by milestones.
- Forecast: for your project budget is a cost estimate or a prediction over a period of time.
- In project management, a budget is considered a deliverable. It is a success metric. The project budget is a tool to communicate exactly what is needed and when it is needed with stakeholders.
- Budget creation takes place in the initiation phase of your project.
- you may be tasked with obtaining approvals for spending. Most companies have a signing or spending policy. This usually outlines who has the authority to commit resources or incur costs or other obligations on behalf of the company.
- you will have to prioritize where you allocate funds within the project to ensure maximum output.
- The project manager will collaborate with people on the project to create their estimations.
- The budgeting process usually happens in conjunction with the scheduling process because the steps of the scheduling process are highly dependent on the costs.
- It's common for the project sponsor to review and approve the estimation costs. And if necessary, adjust and reallocate funds for the project, then the CEO or COO are the ones giving the okay or the final sign-off.
- you will have to prioritize where you allocate funds within the project to ensure maximum output.
- most projects are created to:
 - improve workforce productivity.
 - increase revenue.
 - attempt to save costs within an organization.
- a project manager must show the requested amount of money was used in order to secure enough budget for future projects.
- project managers must account for:
 - understanding stakeholder needs: know exactly what stakeholders expect from this project in order to deliver.
 - budgeting for surprise expenses
 - maintaining adaptability,

- reviewing and reforecasting throughout the entire project. which means creating a separate revised budget based on how your project is tracking.
- Factors to consider when creating a budget:
 - resource cost rates. Some recourses like: labor, tools, equipment, materials, and software.
 - reserve analysis: Performing a reserve analysis will help you, account for any buffer funds you may need. A reserve analysis is a method to check for remaining project resources.
 - contingency budget: is money that is included to cover potentially unforeseen events that aren't accounted for in a cost estimate.
 - and cost of quality: refers to all of the costs that are incurred to prevent issues with products, processes, or tasks. Includes:
 - prevention costs.
 - appraisal costs.
 - internal failure costs.
 - external failure costs.

Budgeting best practices:

- **Reference historical data:** review previous projects and learn from them.
- **Utilize your team, mentors, or manager:** ask for your team to double check your work and documents.
- **Time-phase your budget:** enable track and compare planned versus actual costs over time and manage changes to your budget as necessary.
- **Check, check, and double check:** Make sure that your budget is accurate and error-free.

Categorize different types of costs:

- **Direct costs:**
 - Wages and salaries of employees and contractors
 - Materials costs
 - Equipment rental costs
 - Software licenses
 - Project-related travel and transportation costs
 - Staff training
- **Indirect costs** They are also referred to as **overhead costs**
 - Administrative costs
 - Utilities
 - Insurance
 - General office equipment
 - Security

baseline budget is an estimate of project costs that you start with at the beginning of your project.

reserve analysis will help you account for any buffer funds you may need. **contingency budget.**

Recourses and tactics to avoid overestimation and underestimation:

- researching historical data: you can always review past projects that are similar to yours to get an idea of what your project could entail.
- leveraging experts: Leveraging experts means gathering their insights to do something more effectively.
- the bottom-up approach: means thinking about all the parts of a project from the beginning to the end and making a list of them all.
- confirming accuracy:
- setting your baseline: the dollar amount that you'll use to measure against, to find out if you're on track or not.

Miscellaneous: is a term that we use to represent additional items that are not included in any of the other areas.

Fixed cost: that won't change over the course of the project.

- As a standard practice: account for five percent of the overall project budget as our buffer.
- every project will have an estimated cost and a final cost. Your goal is to get your estimated cost as close to the final cost as possible.
- Monitoring the budget is crucial for a project manager to enforce accountability in terms of spending.
- Milestones are a great opportunity to re-review the budget to identify if anything needs to be reset or revisited throughout the project.
- **Fixed contracts** are usually paid for when certain milestones are reached.
- **time and materials' contracts** are usually paid for monthly based on the hours worked and other fees associated with the work, like travel and meals.
- **Cost control:** is a practice where a project manager identifies factors that might impact their budget and then creates effective actions to minimize variances.
- It is much better to be proactive with your budget than to be reactive with your budget.
- To control costs, consider the following:
 - o you should establish a sign-off plan and inform the appropriate stakeholders of any changes that occur.
 - o manage changes as they're made. This involves updating forecasts or estimates and tracking everything.
 - o accept that budget misses will happen.
 - o The best option is to adequately account for, adapt, and manage your budget with that risk in mind.

Budget pre-allocation: budget is already set before the project starts, which can lead to cost estimations taking place before the scope of the project is completely defined.

total cost of ownership (TCO): takes into account multiple elements that contribute to the cost of an item. It factors in the expenses associated with a product or service over its lifetime, rather than just upfront costs.

Scope creep is when changes, growth, and other factors affect the project's scope at any point after the project begins. Some factors that may lead to scope creep:

- A vague Statement of Work (SoW).
- Conversations and agreements about the project that aren't officially documented.
- Unattainable timeframes and deadlines.
- Last-minute asks from priority stakeholders.

Cash flow is the inflow and outflow of cash on your project.

CAPEX (capital expenses) are an organization's major, long-term, upfront expenses, such as buildings, equipment, and vehicles.

OPEX (operating expenses) are the short-term expenses that are required for the day-to-day tasks involved in running the company, such as wages, rent, and utilities.

contingency reserves. = buffers

management reserves are used to cover the costs of unidentified risks.

procurement means obtaining all of the materials, services, and supplies required to complete the project.

Vendors are individuals or businesses who provide essential goods and services.

vendor management is often a matter of sourcing for a specific service or talent and then managing that relationship. entails sourcing vendors, getting quotes for their work, deciphering which vendors will best fulfill your needs, negotiating their contracts, setting deadlines for them, evaluating performance, and ensuring payments are made.

External resources are people outside the company who can help with tasks, providing complementary skills to those that exist inside the organization.

Procurement process steps:

- Initiating: defining what help you may need outside of your current resources to hit the project goals.
- Selecting: which entails deciding what supplies you need and which vendors you'll go through.
- contract writing: which is where the contracts are developed, reviewed, and signed. pay close attention to the inclusions and exclusions in the vendor's offer. you will almost always want to consult with a legal and compliance team to ensure that everything in the contract is ethical and legal.
- Control: which is when you make payments, set up logistics and requirements to maintain quality, and ensure the service agreement is being met.
- Completing: which is where you measure the success of the procurement.

There are differences in procurement in the context of Agile versus traditional:

- Agile procurement:
 - o Agile procurement management is often more collaborative, with both the project team and the end supplier than traditional approaches.
 - o There is a heavy emphasis on the relationship between these parties.
 - o The whole project team plays a larger role in identifying what needs to be procured.

- Agile procurement management tends to have a living contract.
- Traditional procurement:
 - focus on standard contracts with clear terms and deliverables.
 - project manager may be responsible for end-to-end procurement instead of the entire team providing input.
 - he contracts may feature lengthy and extensive documentation

For each procurement process step there is a document to be created:

- in the initiating phase, a nondisclosure agreement (NDA). The purpose of an NDA is to keep confidential information within the organization.
- In the selecting phase, a request for proposal (RFP). outlines the details and requirements of an organization's project to be passed on to vendors. So, you can then select which vendor might be the best for your project. It typically includes:
 - overview of the project.
 - the desired outcomes.
 - goals
 - budget
 - deadlines
 - milestones
 - contact information
- In the contracting phase, a statement of work (SOW). A statement of work is a document that clearly lays out the products and services a vendor or contractor will provide for the organization. It includes the organization's needs and the vendor's needs. May ask SMEs and legal advisors for advice.

After completing the procurement.

- nearly always be laws in place that you'll need to follow around topics like fair and ethical trade.
- you need to ensure that the various stakeholders who are representing the business are adhering to these policies and processes too. Policies like prevent discrimination and practicing adequate corporate social responsibility.
- You need to be aware of any pertinent meetings regarding legal or compliance issues, and you as a project manager will have to remind the team about when those meetings are being held.
- For some company to be in a scandal, that usually means that the team probably should have done more research in the procurement process.
- **Project managers have a big job when deciphering whether or not every aspect of their project is sourced ethically.**

Steps to safeguard ethical procurement:

- knowing your business' legal requirements. According to the PMI's Code of Ethics, "honesty, responsibility, respect, and fairness are the values that drive ethical conduct for the project management profession".
 - Un-ethical risks:

- bribery or corruption. Such as to offer a certain percentage of an awarded contract—also known as a *kickback*—to an official who can ensure that their company wins the bid.
 - sole-supplier sourcing.
 - interaction with state-owned entities.
- **Stick to your ethical codes.**
- **Test your ethics.** When you face an ethical dilemma, ask yourself:
 - **Shame:** Would you be ashamed if someone knew what you did?
 - **Community:** Would you want your friends to know the decision you made?
 - **Legal:** Would you face legal action if you took this action?
 - **Situation:** Would your actions be justified in this situation?
 - **Consequence:** Would a negative outcome be worth your actions?

To ensure your procurement is ethical, you should make sure that stakeholders adhere to governmental policies and adequate corporate social responsibility. You should also know your company's business requirements, seek out the code of ethics for your profession, and if necessary, consult with an SME.

Risk management:

- A **risk**: is a potential event which can occur and can impact your project. Risks are hypothetical
- An **issue** is a known or real problem that can affect the ability to complete a task.
- a risk is an event that could potentially happen. If the event actually happens, then the risk becomes an issue.
- In other words, risks are the big what-ifs and issues are things that currently impact a project.
- **Risk management**: is the process of identifying and evaluating potential risks and issues that could impact a project.
- Risk management is important because:
 - what could go wrong with your project.
 - It also tells you who you need to consult about the risk.
 - how the potential risk could be mitigated.
- if you don't plan ahead, you may put your project at risk of not meeting its project goal, its timelines, or success criteria.
- by failing to plan for risks, you also fail to think through the many different ways that your project could pivot and still meet its goals. Even if an issue does arise.
- When issues you did not think of arise, it is important to keep calm, figure out the root cause of the problem, and come up with a solution.
- Risk management could involve:
 - Identify the risk. identify and define potential project risks with your team.
 - Analyze the risk. determine their likelihood and potential impact to your project.
 - Evaluate the risk. use the results of your risk analysis to determine which risks to prioritize.
 - Treat the risk. make a plan for how to treat and manage each risk.
 - Monitor and control the risk. assign team members to monitor, track, and mitigate risks.
- Risk management could also help you identify opportunities.

- **Opportunity:** is a potential positive outcome of a risk that may bring additional value to a project.
- Some examples of opportunities include:
 - o Completing a milestone ahead of schedule
 - o Discounted materials
 - o Availability of additional resources (people, investments, equipment)

Uncertainty responses:

THREAT RESPONSE	GENERIC STRATEGY	OPPORTUNITY RESPONSE
Avoid	Eliminate uncertainty	Exploit
Transfer	Allocate ownership	Share
Mitigate	Modify exposure	Enhance
Accept	Include in baseline	Ignore

Tools and techniques to identify risks:

- Brainstorming: identifying risks with the team because it allows groups to spontaneously share ideas without judgment. A tool to use during brainstorming is:
 - o cause-and-effect diagram: also, sometimes known as a fishbone diagram. It shows the possible causes of an event or risk.
 - o risk register: is a table or chart that contains your list of risks.
 - Risk assessment: is the stage of risk management where qualities of a risk are estimated or measured. Tools to use when assessing risks:
 - o A probability and impact matrix: a tool used to prioritize project risks. When creating one consider:
 - Impact refers to the damage a risk could cause if it occurs. Impact is also determined on a scale of high, medium, and low.
 - Probability is the likelihood that a risk will occur.
 - **Inherent risk** is the measure of a risk calculated by its probability and impact.
- The way you view and manage each risk will be determined based on your organization's **risk appetite**, which refers to the willingness of an organization to accept the possible outcomes of a risk.

Working on fishbone diagrams:

- **Define the problem:** define what the problem entails. adds the problem to the head of his fishbone diagram.
- **Identify the categories:** think of the types of categories that could be causing the problem, such as “people,” “technology,” “materials,” “transportation”. Then add them at the top and bottom of the lists to the left of the problem
- **Brainstorm the causes:** reach out to for team for help in identifying these possible causes. fill in the lists with some of the causes that could be related to each category.
 - o **Pro tip:** Brainstorming should be a judgment-free zone. Encourage the flow of information related to the categories and try not to rule things out. When dealing with human factors, steer clear of naming individuals; instead, focus solely on behaviors.

- **Analyze the causes:** identify the root cause of the existing problem so can figure out how to mitigate it. Note that *one* cause of a problem isn't necessarily the *root cause*.
 - o **Pro tip:** Fishbone diagrams are tools that can be useful during any phase of the project. When you use them in risk planning, you are trying to identify the possible causes of a problem that may or may not occur. When you use them in the execution phase, you are trying to find the root cause of an issue that has already occurred.

Example final fishbone diagram:

Common types of risks:

- time risks: refers to the possibility that project tasks will take longer than anticipated to complete.
- budget risks: refers to the possibility that the cost of a project will increase due to poor planning or expanding the project scope.
- scope risks: refers to the possibility that a project won't produce the results outlined in the project goals.
- Other external risks:
 - o referring to risks that result from factors outside of the company that you have little to no control over. Such as environmental risk, like a major storm, or a legal risk, like a change in regulatory requirements.
- there are endless types of risks.
- A single point of failure is a risk that has the potential to be catastrophic and halt work across a project.
- A dependency is a relationship between two project tasks, where the start or completion of one depends on the start or completion of the other. Therefore, they are a huge source of risk. If you don't plan for dependencies, you might risk and impact your budget schedule or project outcome. There are two types of dependencies:

- Internal: refer to dependencies within the project that you and your team have control over.
- External: dependencies that you have no control over.

Single point of failure: such as Having only one SME familiar with a critical system on your team is an example of a single point of failure risk. Because they will offer only a single perspective.

Four types of risk mitigation

- **Avoid:** This strategy seeks to sidestep—or avoid—the situation as a whole.
- **Minimize:** Mitigating a risk involves trying to minimize the catastrophic effects that it could have on the project. The key to minimizing risk starts with realizing that the risk exists. That is why you will usually hear mitigation strategies referred to as *workarounds*.
- **Transfer:** The strategy of transferring shifts the responsibility of handling the risk to someone else.
- **Accept:** you can accept the risk as the normal cost of doing business.
 - **Active acceptance of risk** usually means setting aside extra funds to pay your way out of trouble.
 - **Passive acceptance of risk** is the “do nothing” approach. While passive acceptance may be reasonable for smaller risks, it is not recommended for most single point of failure risks.

Types of dependencies:

- **Finish to Start (FS):** in this type Task A must be completed before Task B can start.

- **Finish to Finish (FF):** In this model, Task A must finish before Task B can finish.

- **Start to Start (SS):** In this model, Task A can't begin until Task B begins. This means Tasks A and B start at the same time and run in parallel.

- **Start to Finish (SF):** In this model, Task A must begin before Task B can be completed.

Risk mitigation: planning is about finding ways to eliminate or reduce the impact of potential risks to your project.

Four ways to mitigate risk:

- you can avoid it.
- accept it.
- reduce or control it.
- or transfer it.

You can build a mitigation plan using a **decision tree** which is a flowchart that helps visualize the wider impact of a decision on the rest of your project.

risk management plan is a living document that contains information regarding high-level risks and the mitigation plan for each of those risks.

- The plan should be updated regularly to add, or remove risks or include changes to the plan.
- Risk management plan contains mitigation plans, a risk register and a probability and impact matrix.
- inherent risk is the measure of a risk calculated by its probability and impact.
- After you finish planning for your project and risks you need to inform your team mates and stakeholders because if you do not, they might be less equipped when something happens. And failing to communicate risks to stakeholders might erode their trust in you as a project leader.
- You should consider the severity of the identified risk. It is important to communicate early and often with stakeholders about medium- and high-level risks. For low-level risks, something as simple as an email might suffice.

A googler says: program management is about bringing order to chaos.

Communication and documentation:

- **Communication:** is the flow of information. It includes everything that's shared, how it's shared, and with whom.
- Effective communication is:
 - o Clear.
 - o Honest.
 - o Relevant.

- Frequent.
- ★ but not too frequent. There is such a thing as information overload.
- Ways of communication:
 - meetings
 - emails
 - phone calls
 - written documents
 - formal presentations
- needs to happen throughout the entire life cycle of the project.

- **Recognize and understand individual differences:**
 - And that is by:
 - Not making assumptions about your audience’s backgrounds, identities, or experiences.
 - Being mindful of your own biases.
 - Using appropriate, professional, and neutral language.
 - Including, respecting, and being curious about diverse points of view.
- **Brainstorm and craft the appropriate message:**
 - Always think about who are you communicating with because not everyone needs to be communicated with in the same frequency, and be clear about the reasons you are communicating with that person:
 - What channels can your audience use to contact you or the team?
 - Are you conveying information?
 - Are you asking for input?
 - Are you clarifying an issue?
 - Are you resolving a problem?
- **Deliver your message:**
 - Choose which method to communicate by, whether that is in person, in a video conference, over the phone, via email, or in a meeting.

- Also, be sure to:
 - Avoid including any sensitive or potentially private information.
 - Assume everyone at the company will receive the communication.
- **Obtain feedback and incorporate that feedback going forward:**
 - Follow up on your audience:
 - Checking to make sure your message was clear.
 - Asking them for feedback.
 - Encouraging open communication.
 - Responding to questions quickly.

communication plan: organizes and documents the process, types, and expectations of communication for the project.

communication plan needs to address these questions:

- what needs to be communicated?
- who needs to communicate?
- when communication needs to happen?
- why and how to communicate?
- where the information communicated is stored?

Benefits of planning communication:

- improve the overall effectiveness of communication.
- keeps people engaged and motivated throughout the project.
- gets stakeholders involved in effective conversations.

Different people have different ways to absorb information:

- Visual
- Listen
- Read and review
- Talk to someone.
- And you can find about that by asking three questions:
 - What is working in how we communicate with you about the project?
 - What is not working or is not effective in our communications?
 - Where can we improve our communications with you?

Tip for communication plans creation:

- First you need to identify the following:
 - **Project stakeholders:** Have you created a RACI chart or stakeholder map of all your stakeholders?....
 - **Communication frequency and method:** When and how often should you check in with your stakeholders?...
 - **Goals:** What is the goal of your communication?...
 - **Barriers:** Are there any time zone limitations?

- Document and develop:
 - **Add a column for notes.** If a stakeholder is out of office, Add notes to set reminders and any additional relevant details.
 - **Use formatting to highlight any key details in the plan.** Highlight pivotal elements in a different font color or size to stress their importance.
 - **Ensure that the team can access your document.** Share the plan with your team.
 - **Test your plan.** If you are planning a virtual presentation, be sure to test the visual, audio, and other technical aspects in advance.
- Check in:
 - check in with your audience about the effectiveness of your plan.
 - Evaluate where you may be over- or under-sharing information or missing stakeholders.
You can do this through:
 - Anonymous survey forms
 - Polls or open feedback sessions during team meetings
 - One-on-one conversations and check-ins with key stakeholders

Documentation:

- Documentation storage and sharing is very important. Having plans in one place makes communication quicker, easier, and more streamlined.
- Documenting and organizing plans also provide visibility and accountability.
- members of the team and senior stakeholders reference your project plan and associated documents when they need a refresher on timelines or milestones. So having up-to-date plans will help ensure there's no room for misinterpretation or miscommunication.
- managing permissions:
 - Some people you do not want them to know everything about the project, instead summarize the relevant information into a status report for those who need to stay informed of final outcomes but don't need all background information
- big benefit to setting up your project plans and centralizing them in one place: **continuity**
- It's always useful to store guides, manuals, meeting notes, plans, and processes all in a centralized place and clearly labeled.
- it's your job to ensure that project data can be accessed in the future by others
- knowledge management. Is a way to ensure the project data is accessible for making decisions or planning similar projects
- Pro tip: important to determine what kind of information to share with whom and when.
- Only share information on a need-to-know basis. It's your job to present the right information at the right time to the right people.
- personally identifiable information or PII. PII is anything that possibly reveal someone's identity, like a screen name, password, phone number, e-mail address, first or last name, anything like that.
- your goal is to have all of your project resources documented and linked in a way to where you or anyone on the project can access what they need quickly. By using for example, a shared file drive, like Google Drive

- **Tracking:** is a method of following the progress of a project's activities. Measuring project performance regularly to identify deviations from the project plan can help ensure that the project stays on track.
- **Deviation:** is anything that alters your original course of action. Deviations from the project plan can be positive or negative.
- tracking Benefits:
 - o makes key project information transparent, and transparency is essential for accurate decision-making. Also,
 - o helps ensure that you don't risk forgetting something.
 - o tracking helps keep all team members and stakeholders in touch with deadlines and goals.
 - o Tracking is also crucial for recognizing risks and issues that can derail your progress.
 - o tracking helps build confidence that the project is set to be delivered on time, in-scope, and within budget.
- tracking is important because:
 - o like transparency.
 - o risk management
 - o keeping the project on track.
- Objects to tracks:
 - o you should always track the project schedule.
 - o tracking the status of action items, key tasks, and activities.
 - o tasks and key milestones.
 - o costs to ensure that you don't overspend or underspend on project tasks.
 - o key decisions, changes, dependencies, and risks to the project, including any agreed upon scope changes.
- tracking methods:
 - o Gantt chart,
 - o a roadmap,
 - o a burndown chart.
- It's important to remember to select something that the entire team can easily understand, reference, and keep up to date.
- Gantt chart: it's a useful chart for:
 - o staying on schedule
 - o projects with many dependencies or tasks or activities or milestones that are reliant on one another.
 - o It's also a helpful chart for teams with a lot of people, because ownership and responsibilities are explicitly laid out visually.
- Gantt charts are commonly used in Waterfall project management.
- You could use a roadmap when:
 - o a way to track big milestones in your project. Roadmaps outline the project as a whole and provide an overall snapshot of key points—just like an actual roadmap contains points of interest and mile markers.
 - o illustrating how a project should evolve over time to a team and key stakeholders.
- The approach in a roadmap details the main tactics your team will use to reach your goal.

- A roadmap includes a high-level project overview. High-level in this context means a concise summary.
- A burndown chart is the most granular method and it measures time against the amount of work done and the amount of work remaining.
- The burndown chart main uses are to keep the project team on top of targeted completion dates and to keep the team aware of scope creep as it occurs.
- The y-axis or the vertical axis symbolizes the number of tasks left to complete, and the x-axis or the horizontal axis signifies time. Progress gets tracked from the upper left-hand corner of the chart. Or simply it's a two-dimensional Cartesian space.
- If you need to communicate milestones to a large team, you might choose a roadmap. If you have a project with multiple dependencies, you might choose a Gantt chart. If tracking tasks against your deadline is especially important, then the burndown chart might be your best option.
- Burndown charts are typically used by Agile Scrum teams.
- **Project status report** gives an overview of all of the project's common elements and summarizes them in a snapshot. It is an efficient communication tool to convey the latest status in one place for the team and stakeholders.
- The project status report:
 - o **Project name:** The project name should be specific to the purpose of the project.
 - o **Date:** You will create project status reports many times during the course of a project's implementation phase.
- **project status report** gives an overview of all of the project's common elements and summarizes them in a snapshot. And it's useful for:
 - o Improve and simplify communication across the team.
 - o Keep everyone, including key stakeholders, informed.
 - o Request more resources and support (if needed).
 - o Create structure and transparency by recording the project status in a centralized place.
- Status reports contain the following components:
 - o **Project name:**
 - o **Date**
 - o **Summary**
 - o **Status**
 - o **Milestones and tasks**
 - o **issues**
- status report reveals ongoing issues with product and service quality. To help your team stay organized, you'll categorize them as resolved, owned, accepted, or mitigated.
- When your team encounters a major issue, you'll write an escalation email to get support and advice from senior stakeholders.
- Execution and closing phases:
 - o Create a project status report
 - o Conduct a ROAM analysis
 - o Write an escalation email
 - o Create a presentation for your team
 - o plan a meeting to discuss open issues

- Create a report to close the project
- a risk is a potential event that might occur and could impact your project.
- Examples of project risks:
 - a contractor missing a deadline.
 - or introducing a tool such as a communication tool.
 - or unexpected, additional work because of an unforeseen policy.
- A change is anything that alters or impacts the tasks, structures, or processes within a project.
- Changes have negative impact on the project but sometimes (very rarely) it has positive impact.
- Types of changes:
 - New or changing dependencies.
 - Changing priorities.
 - Capacity and people.
 - Limitations on budget and resources.
 - Scope creep.
 - Force majeure.
- Force majeure: means an unforeseen circumstance that prevents someone from fulfilling the contract due to a major crisis such as worldwide crisis.
- To document changes you might use the statement of work or a RACI chart. Or you might use a new documentation such as a change request forms, which is an optional form.
- Change request forms include:
 - A short description of the current situation
 - An in-depth proposal for the necessary changes
 - Background information
- **Dependencies:** are the links that connect one project task to another, and as we mentioned, they're often the greatest source of risk to a project.
- **internal** dependency, which describes the relationship between two tasks within the same project.
- **External** dependencies, on the other hand, refer to tasks that are reliant on outside factors, like regulatory agencies or other projects.
- **Mandatory** dependencies are tasks that are legally or contractually required.
- **discretionary** dependencies are tasks that could occur on their own, but the team saw a need to make those dependencies reliant on one another.
- **Dependency management** is the process of managing all of these interrelated tasks and resources within the project to ensure that your overall project is completed successfully on time and in budget.
- effective dependency management, may be achieved by following four steps:
 - proper identification,
 - recording dependencies,
 - continuous monitoring and control,
 - efficient communication.
- **proper identification.** A project manager will have to brainstorm all possible project dependencies with their team and categorize them accordingly.

- Recording dependencies happens by creating a risk register which is a table or chart that contains your list of risks and dependencies. It should include a description of the dependency, the date, and all activities or tasks that may be impacted by the dependency.
- Continuous monitoring and control: This means you will want to schedule regular meetings to check in on the interrelated tasks, staying up-to-date on any progress being made and double checking for changes that will impact other tasks.
- **Risk exposure (inherent risk):** is a way to measure the potential future loss resulting from a specific activity or event.
- A good method to calculate risk exposure is to build a matrix with the on axis as “risk impact” and the other as “probability”.
- The ROAM technique which stands for resolved, owned, accepted, and mitigated is used to help manage actions after risks arise.
 - o Resolved: If a risk has been eliminated and will not be a problem
 - o Owned: If you give a team member ownership over a certain risk and entrust them to handle it.
 - o Accepted: it has been agreed that nothing will be done about it.
 - o Mitigated: if some action has been taken such that the risk has been mitigated, either reducing the likelihood of it occurring or reducing the impact to the project
- A **contingency plan**, on the other hand, is mostly related to funds the project manager keeps aside (outside of the planned project budget) to support any of these known risk response plans if they go beyond the planned amount or to manage any unforeseen risks during execution.

One way to remove obstacles is to escalate.

- **Escalation:** is the process of enlisting the help of higher-level project leadership or management to remove an obstacle, clarify or reinforce priorities, and validate next steps. Benefit of escalation:
 - o act as a checks and balances tool
 - o result in speedy decision-making
 - o Reduce frustration
 - o Encourage participation
- Before starting work on a project, the project manager, the team, and the project sponsor should establish **escalation standards** and practices.
- **When to escalate:** A project manager should escalate an issue at the first sign of critical problems in the project.
- **Critical problems** are issues that may cause a delay to a major project milestone, issues that cause budget overruns, issues that can result in the loss of a customer, and issues that push back the estimated project completion date.
- Escalation is great for preventing two common issues within a project:
 - o trench wars
 - o bad compromises.
- **Trench wars** occur when two peers or groups can't seem to come to an agreement, and neither party is willing to give in.
- **bad compromise** occurs when two parties settle on a so-called solution, but the end product still suffers.

- you'll need to tailor your communication tactics based on the subject matter and recipient.
- when communicating a small change that will affect an individual, it's a good idea to send an email
- When there's a big change within your project that impacts more than one person and is likely to change the budget, deadline, or scope of the project, you'll probably want to have a team meeting.
- A timeout means taking a moment away from the project in order to take a breath, regroup, and adjust the game plan.
- This timeout is a chance for the project team to evaluate the changes so they can adjust the plan as needed.
- A retrospective is a meeting that focuses on identifying the contributing causes of an incident or pattern of incidents without blaming one individual.
- While conducting a retrospective, you should always assume that everyone has good intentions and did the right thing with the information they had, whether or not it worked out well in the end.
- To write an effective escalation email:
 - o Maintain a friendly tone: it is important to address issues with grace.
 - o State your connection to the project: Introduce yourself early in the email.
 - o Explain the problem: Clearly state the problem you need to solve.
 - o Explain the consequences: Describe specifically how this issue is negatively impacting the project.
 - o Make a request: you propose a solution and state what you need from the recipient.
- **Quality** is when you fulfill the outlined requirements for the deliverable and meet or exceed the needs or expectations of your customers.
- the four main concepts of quality management:
 - quality standards.
 - quality planning.
 - quality assurance.
 - quality control.
- **Quality standards** provide requirements, specifications, or guidelines that can be used to ensure that products, processes, or services are fit for achieving the desired outcome. And it is often set at the beginning of the project.
- **Quality planning** refers specifically to the actions of a project manager or the team to establish and conduct a process for identifying and determining exactly which standards of quality are in fact relevant to the project as a whole
- **Quality assurance**, often shortened to QA, is all about evaluating if your project is moving towards delivering a high-quality service or product.
- **quality control (QC)**: involves monitoring project results and delivery to determine if they are meeting desired results or not. If not, then alternative actions should be taken.

Fostering relationships with communication:

- strategic communication with a customer or client can instill a sense of confidence that you're doing a good job and that you're a trustworthy partner.

- It's important to ask open-ended questions and actively listen to understand the customer's current state versus their desired state.
- set clear expectations about when they'll communicate certain things to their customers.
- if you reach a point in the project where you can't possibly move forward without the client's help and input, you'll have to communicate the issue to them calmly and with empathy.
- you'll want to be considerate of your customers' feelings and limitations. You can do this by exhibiting empathy:
 - o understanding their frustrations.
 - o addressing them.
 - o and finding a solution that's beneficial for both of you.
- Good customer service results in choosing to go back to the same places because you liked the way that you were treated and the service you received (even if you had an issue), versus bad customer service which results choosing not to go back to those places if you don't receive that level of care.
- soft skills like:
 - o negotiation
 - o empathetic listening,
 - o trust-building

will help create a good relationship between you and your customers.

- The best way to get an idea of what customers and users want is to ask them, there are a few ways we can streamline that information. Some common ones are:
 - o feedback surveys
 - o user acceptance tests
- **Feedback surveys** are a survey in which users provide feedback on features of your product that they like or dislike. these surveys can take place as you design, before you launch, or after you've launched.
- **user acceptance test:** or a UAT, is a test that helps a business makes sure that a product or solution works for its users. UATs are sometimes referred to as "beta tests.".
- In a **typical UAT setting:**
 - o Welcome users and thank them
 - o Present your product
 - o Start UAT test cases
 - o give users a visual representation or mock up
 - o identify edge cases.
 - o recap your findings, identify bugs or issues, and prioritize which issues need to be addressed first.
- **critical user journey** is a sequence of steps a user follows to accomplish tasks in your product.
- **Edge cases** are rare—outliers that the original requirements didn't account for. They deal with the extreme maximums and minimums of parameters.
- **Objectives** of UAT:
 - o Demonstrate that the product, service, or process is behaving in expected ways in real-world scenarios.

- Show that the product, service, or process is working as intended.
- Identify issues that need to be addressed before considering the project as done.
- **best practices** for an effective UAT:
 - Define and write down your acceptance criteria.

Acceptance criteria are pre-established standards or requirements that a product, service, or process must meet.
 - Create the test cases for each item that you are testing.

test case is a sequence of steps and its expected results.
 - Select your users carefully.
 - Write the UAT scripts based on user stories

user story is an informal, general explanation of a feature written from the perspective of the end user.
 - Communicate with users and let them know what to expect.
 - Prepare the testing environment for UAT.
 - Provide a step-by-step plan to help guide users through the testing process.
 - Compile notes in a single document and record any issues that are discovered.
- **Managing UAT feedback**
 - **Bugs or issues:** Users might report technical issues, also known as **bugs**, or other types of issues after performing UAT.
 - **Change requests:** Sometimes the user might suggest minor changes to the product, service, or process after UAT.
- **Continuous improvement** is an ongoing effort to improve products or services. It helps ensure that a product steadily makes its way toward the best possible outcome.
- Continuous improvement begins with recognizing when processes and tasks need to be created, eliminated, or improved.
- **Process improvement** is the practice of identifying, analyzing, and improving existing processes to enhance the performance of your team and to develop best practices or to optimize consumer experiences.
- **control** is an experiment or observation designed to minimize the effects of variables.
- **Control groups** are representative samples that help you to determine that the differences between your experimental groups and the norm is due to your changes, rather than something else.
- **Data-driven improvement frameworks:** are techniques used to make decisions based on actual data.
 - DMAIC, and pronounced (“demaisy”) stands for define, measure, analyze, improve, and control.
 - define the business problem, goals, resources, project scope, and project timeline.
 - measure. Here, you'll conduct performance metrics and data collection to establish baselines and measure success.
 - analyze. Work to find the root causes of problems and understand their impact.
 - improve. This means implementing a reasonable solution to the problem

- control. This is where you'll implement the changes and stay on top of monitoring the updated processes you've established.
 - PDCA is a four-step process that focuses on identifying a problem, fixing that issue, assessing whether the fix was successful, and fine-tuning the final fix.
 - plan. Here, you'll identify the issue and root cause and brainstorm solutions to the problem.
 - do, or fix the problem.
 - check. Compare your results to the goal to find out if the problem is fixed.
 - act, or fine-tune the fix to ensure continuous improvement.
- These frameworks help you to:
 - identify issues,
 - reduce errors,
 - optimize your processes.

project is one single-focused endeavor.

program is a collection of projects.

portfolio is a collection of projects and programs across the whole organization.

Retrospective: A retrospective is a workshop or meeting that gives project teams time to reflect on a project. sometimes known as retros,

- should happen throughout the life cycle of a project, but mostly are implemented after major milestones, or most commonly, after a project is completed.
- Retrospectives serve three main **purposes**:
 - they encourage team building.
 - they facilitate improved collaboration on future projects.
 - they promote positive changes in future procedures and processes.
- The emphasis in retrospectives is on continuous improvement and change, instead of recycling old— and potentially bad—habits, procedures, and processes.
- **Reasons** to hold a retrospective:
 - missed deadlines or expectations.
 - miscommunications between stakeholders.
 - the end of a sprint.
 - after product launches and landings.
 - record key lessons that other people might learn from
- the way you decide to conduct a retrospective can vary. There's no exact formula or template for a productive retrospective; the way you choose to structure your retrospective will depend on your team and workplace.
- Retrospectives best practices:
 - Ensure that the discussions are blameless, and to do that do the following:
 - changing perspective
 - switching from "you" language to "we" language.
 - reflecting on the positive aspects of projects too.
- When conducting a retrospective:
 - maintain a positive tone throughout the process.

- be considerate of teams outside of your own
 - Go over the chain of events in the same way that they happened in real time.
- in general, the retrospective should be considered a positive experience where team members feel comfortable sharing their feedback.
- **How** to create a retrospective:
 - Before the meeting create project summary, which includes:
 - Goals and objectives
 - Duration
 - Team members
 - Methodology
 - Key accomplishments: begin the meeting on a positive note by encouraging the team to list out what went well.
 - Lessons learned: The team also discusses things that need improvement, as well as instances when they were fortunate that things went in their favor.
 - Action items: the team turn their lessons into action items.
 - Future considerations: The team identifies specific considerations for their research process, timeline, and team dynamic.
 - Resources and notes: add the project notes which the team said they found valuable. They also include the names of vendors and software that the team used.
- Data-informed decision making:
 - **Data** is a collection of facts or information
 - **Data analysis:** is the collection of data in order to draw conclusions and make data-informed decisions.
 - companies source data on customer behavior and customer demand to provide better services and create new products.
 - You can use data to:
 - make better decisions,
 - solve problems,
 - understand performance,
 - improve processes,
 - understand your users.
 - A **metric** is a quantifiable measurement that is used to track and assess a business objective. And they are two types:
 - productivity metrics
 - quality metrics.
 - **Productivity** typically measures progress and output over time. track the effectiveness and efficiency of your project and include metrics like:
 - milestones,
 - tasks,
 - projections,
 - duration.
 - **projection** is how you predict an outcome based on the information you have now.
 - The **duration** of a project is the total time it takes to complete a project from start to finish.
 - **Quality** metrics relates to achieving acceptable outcomes, include metrics such as:

- the number of changes,
 - issues,
 - cost variance
- The number of changes during the project or project scope helps to monitor risks.
- Changes show any inconsistencies from the initial requirements of the project.
- **change log** is a record of all of the notable changes on a project.
- **An issue** is a known and real problem that may affect the ability to complete a task.
- **cost variance**. It illustrates the difference between the actual cost and the budget cost.
- You could use Project management tools like Workfront and JIRA. Data analysis tools like Tableau
- Project managers at Google use a sub-set of metrics called **happiness metrics** that also relate to quality, these metrics measure aspects such as **visual appeal**, how likely they are to **recommend**, and **ease of use**.
- Another set of metrics related to quality are adoption and engagement. **Adoption** refers to whether or not a product, service or process is accepted and used. **Engagement** refers to the degree to which it is used—the frequency of use, amount of time spent using it, and the range of use.
- Return on investment specifically looks at the dollar amount earned for the amount invested in a project, it looks at the specific benefit from the project divided by the costs.
- **signal** is an observable change, and it can help you to determine the overall health of your project and identify early signs that something isn't quite right.
- How to know which data is important:
 - Identify which tasks contribute most to the overall goal.
 - prioritize the data or metrics that are most valuable to stakeholders.
- Stakeholders can look to your project plan for a high-level overview of answers to important questions, success criteria, artifacts, and the overall health of your project.
- **Data ethics** is the study and evaluation of moral challenges related to data collection and analysis.
- Businesses apply data ethics practices so they can:
 - Comply with regulations
 - Show that they are trustworthy
 - Ensure fair and reasonable data usage
 - Minimize biases
 - Develop a positive public perception
- Data ethics **principles**:
 - **Data privacy** is a key part of data ethics. Data privacy deals with the proper handling of data. And you can ensure the privacy of your data by:
 - **Increasing data privacy awareness.**
 - **Using security tools.**
 - **Anonymizing data.**
 - **Data bias** is a type of error that tends to skew results in a certain direction. Types of biases:

- **Sampling bias** is when a sample is not representative of the population as a whole.
 - **Observer bias** is the tendency for different people to observe things differently.
 - **Interpretation bias** is the tendency to always interpret situations that don't have obvious answers in a strictly positive or negative way, when there are many ways to understand the data
 - **Confirmation bias** is the tendency to search for or interpret information in a way that confirms pre-existing beliefs.
- Project managers will often apply data analysis to look for repeated behaviors and to find a solution based on data predictions.
- **Quantitative data** includes statistical and numerical facts. Such as KPI data, track the number of open and closed tasks per team member.
- **qualitative data** which describes the subjective qualities or things that can't be measured with numerical data. Such as opinion-based feedback surveys.
- There are six steps for data analysis:
 - **Ask:** ask key questions to help frame your analysis, and another part is identifying your stakeholders and understanding their expectations.
 - **Prepare:** collect and store the data you will use for the upcoming analysis process.
 - **Process:** “clean” your data
 - **Analyze:** take a close look at your data to draw conclusions, make predictions, and decide on next steps.
 - **Share:** **Share** your findings use **data visualization** to organize your data
 - **Act:** put your analysis into action
- **Storytelling** is the process of turning facts into narrative to communicate something to your audience. Stories usually have a beginning, middle, and end. There are six steps for storytelling:
 - define your audience: know who you're presenting to.
 - collect the data: Find the data that connects to the question you want to answer.
 - filter and analyze the data: vet it for credibility and filter the information.
 - choose a visual representation: Visualizations are a great way to help people remember the information you're presenting and are an essential piece of storytelling.
 - shape the story: tie it all (your data) together into one cohesive narrative.
 - gather your feedback: before you present, you do a trial run.
- **Data visualization:** is the graphical representation of information to facilitate understanding.
 - they help filter information by focusing the audience on the most important data points and insights.
 - they condense long ideas and facts into a single image or representation
 - help the viewer make sense of and remember the information being presented.
- A **dashboard** is a type of user interface, typically a graph or summary chart, that provides a snapshot view of your project's progress or performance.
- **KPI (key performance indicator):** is a measurable value or metric that demonstrates how effective an organization is at achieving key objectives.

- **countdown** that shows the number of days until project launch or the percentage of the number of issues resolved.
- In contrast to burndown chart **Column charts** are useful for comparing different activities or comparing progress over time.
- **Infographics**: are visual representations of information, such as data or facts, and are typically in the form of what we call at Google a "one-pager" or a "one-sheeter." The difference is that they're typically concise summaries of that data.
- **scatter plot**, sometimes referred to as a scatter chart or scatter graph, uses dots to represent values for two different variables.
- Pie charts show us the **composition** of something.
- **Line graphs** are a great tool for visually showing change over time.
- Brene Brown: in "the power of vulnerability": "if you can't measure it, it does not exist"
- Giving effective presentations:
 - o precise
 - o flexible
 - o Memorable
- Identify the problem you're solving for your audience and
- remove any content that dilutes your narrative.
- One way I ensure that my slideshow presentations are as precise as they can be is by using a technique called "**designing for five seconds**." The idea is that your audience should be able to understand a slide within five seconds.
- To be **flexible** do the following:
 - o Consider the approach you'd take if you had to shorten your presentation, unexpectedly.
 - o Practice to avoid mistakes that could distract from your message.
 - o identify and come up with answers to potential questions.
 - o imagine and prepare for possible objections.
- To make your story **memorable**:
 - o Use stories or include repetition to help your audience remember the information moving forward.
 - o be aware of your body language.
 - Maintain an upright posture.
 - rest your hands at your side.
 - try elevating your tone of voice.
 - Pace yourself by using intentional pauses.
 - Make eye contact with your audience.
 - keep your facial expressions warm and friendly.
 - have confidence
- **Prepare** to your presentation as following:
 - o Get clear on your goals and the purpose of your presentation.
 - o Seek input and set expectations.
 - o Create a delivery plan.
 - o Be mindful of your audience's time.
 - o Develop a strategy for making your presentation memorable.
- Practice for your presentation:

- Guide your audience through your presentation.
- Do a mock presentation with your team.
- Schedule time to practice.
- Be prepared for surprises.
- The presentation and pace:
 - Get right to the point.
 - Check your pace.
- Follow up

Team work:

- Besides that, the project manager has to deliver their project they need to:
 - support the people on the team to do their best work
 - enable people to build things they're proud of.
- A **team** is a group of people who plan, solve problems, make decisions, and review progress in service of a specific project, or objective.
- **workgroups**, which we define as being based on organizational or managerial hierarchy. Though people within a workgroup might be working toward a common goal, their work is more likely to be coordinated, controlled or assigned by single person or entity.
- **Teamwork** is an effective collaborative way of working in which each person is committed to and heading toward a shared goal.
- Team work is **crucial** because:
 - Fosters creativity.
 - encourages accountability.
 - helps you get stuff done
- Factors have impact on team **effectiveness**:
 - psychological safety: refers to an individual's perception, of the consequences of taking an Interpersonal risk.
 - Dependability: On dependable teams, members are reliable and complete their work on time.
 - structure and clarity: refer to an individual's understanding of job expectations, knowledge of how to meet those expectations and the consequences of their performance.
 - Meaning: finding a sense of purpose either in the work itself or in the results of that work.
 - Impact: the belief that the results of one's work matters and creates change.
- How project managers build highly functioning teams:
 - **They create systems that turn chaos into order:** You find the system through the chaos and help other people to find it, too.
 - **They communicate and listen:** it's your job to ensure that everyone on your team is on the same page regarding the status of your project. your responsibility to regularly connect with individual teammates.
 - **They promote trust and psychological safety:** It's your job to create a team atmosphere where different opinions are welcome, and all members remain respectful of one another.
 - **They demonstrate empathy and create motivation:** "there's no I in team,", You can demonstrate empathy for your teammates by being present, listening, and asking

questions. Recognition tells people that they're doing the right things, and motivates them, be sure to recognize good work, and not just heroic efforts.

- **They delegate responsibility and prioritize:** By prioritizing tasks, you reduce ambiguity and provide clarity for your team.
- **They celebrate team's success:** This includes celebrating big and small wins like reaching a milestone or receiving positive feedback from stakeholders.
- there may come a time when you will need to prioritize the needs of your team over the wants of your stakeholders. This is called providing “**air cover**” for your team, and it is an important part of managing a project. And some ways to provide air cover:
 - **Saying “No” without explicitly saying “No”:**
 - You can gently push back with a polite explanation that their request won't be possible to complete.
 - You can politely offer to get back to the stakeholder with your response. And offer an alternative later.
 - **Intervening from behind the scenes**
 - Managing the expectations of your stakeholder while looping in relevant teammates on a need-to-know basis is essential. This allows your team to focus on their work without the possibility of an increased workload or an unnecessary distraction.
- **Bruce Tushman** stages of **team development:**
 - **Forming,** the team are just getting to know one another, you should clarify project goals, roles, and context about the project.
 - **Storming,** frustration might emerge. it's your job to focus on conflict resolution. Listen as the team addresses problems to solve and share insights on how the team might better function as a unit.
 - **Norming:** the team has resolved some of its internal conflict by establishing new norms. You should codify the team norms, ensuring that the team is aware of those norms and reinforce them when needed.
 - **Performing:** the team works together relatively seamlessly, should focus on delegating, motivating and providing feedback to keep up the team's momentum.
 - **Adjourning:** the project is wrapping up, it's time for the team to disband. should set up time to celebrate the final milestones and success of the project as a group.
- **Team dynamics** refer to the forces both conscious and unconscious, that impact team behavior and performance. And it's important to be managed because:
 - teams have individuals with different skill sets, varying degrees of autonomy, and competing priorities.
 - helps you to create a collaborative and psychologically safe environment.
 - help you understand how to motivate your team.
- **Ethical leadership:** is a form of leadership that promotes and values honesty, justice, respect, community and integrity. And can be promoted by:
 - defining and aligning values within your team.
 - demonstrating how adhering to those values benefits the mission of the organization.
- To **demonstrate** ethical leadership companies can create:

- raise their viewpoints.
- be heard.
- receive follow-ups from company leaders on employee concerns.
- Ethical leadership is closely tied to inclusive leadership. If **ethical leadership's aim** is to create forums where employees' concerns can be heard, **inclusive leadership aims** to put what we've heard into action to create an environment that encourages. And empowers each and every member of our community.
- **Inclusive leadership** is when everyone's unique identity, background and experiences are respected, valued and integrated into how the team operates.
- **diversity** is the set of differences each of us possesses, whether visible or invisible that gives us each a unique perspective on the world and our work.
- **Inclusion** is what the team does with that diversity of thought and perspective.
- three ways that managers can lead inclusively:
 - fostering a culture of respect: That means
 - modeling the values of your organization.
 - taking appropriate action if misconduct occurs.
 - Creating an environment in which team members feel comfortable speaking up with concerns.
 - recognizing team contributions regularly.
 - creating equal opportunity to succeed.
 - You do this through regular communication,
 - accessible documentation.
 - regular check-ins with the team to listen, share information, ask and answer questions and provide support.
 - inviting and integrating diverse perspectives. You do this by:
 - creating a sense of psychological safety on the team.
 - inviting teammates to share their thoughts, ideas and concerns, regardless of their role or rank on the team.

Ethics can be defined as the principles of conduct governing an individual or a group.

Here at Google, our code of conduct makes clear the expectations that we have for our employees and board members. It is possible that the organizations you will join throughout your career will have codes of conduct, too.

helpful guide for **ethical decision-making**:

- **Recognize an ethical issue:** you can begin to question the ethics of an issue by asking yourself questions about the nature of the issue.
- **Get the facts:** Decide what you should do about the issue, and seek answers as needed. Consult with the right people to consider all of the options available to you.
- **Evaluate alternative actions:** You can evaluate alternative actions by asking yourself questions. you may want to elicit the opinion of others before deciding on an alternative action.
- **Make a decision and test it:** Once you have chosen an option, test it by imagining the reaction to your choice from a person whose opinion you value.

- **Act and reflect on the outcome:** Consider how to carry out your decision with thoughtfulness and care, and after you act, consider the results of your decision.

Influencing: is the ability to alter another person's thinking or behaviors.

Leadership expert, Dr. Jay A Conger identifies the steps to **effective influencing** as:

- **establish credibility:** During this step, you make the case for why your audience should listen to you. And credibility comes from two sources:
 - o Expertise
 - o Relationships.
- **frame for common ground:** make the case for how your idea can benefit your audience.
- **provide evidence:** you'll make your case through hard data and persuasive storytelling.
- **connect emotionally:** you'll demonstrate to your audience that you're emotionally committed to your idea and you'll do your best to match their emotional state.

Common mistakes people make when trying to influence others:

- approach their audience too aggressively,
- resist compromise,
- focus too much on developing their argument for the idea and not enough time establishing credibility, framing for common ground, providing evidence and connecting emotionally,
- assume that they can work out an agreement through just one conversation.

Most of your power to influence others comes from your power, most power sources fall into two buckets:

- Organizational.
 - o Role: which refers to your position within an organization, or team.
 - o Information. which refers to your level of access, and control over information.
 - o Network: This refers to people you're connected with professionally and personally.
 - o Reputation: refers to how others perceive you overall.
- Personal.
 - o Knowledge: refers to the power that you draw from your expertise in certain subjects, your unique abilities, and skill sets, and even your ability to learn new things.
 - o Expressiveness: your ability to communicate with others.
 - o History: refers to the level of personal history there is between yourself and another person.
 - o Character: refers to other people's view of the qualities that make you: you.

Elita says: "As you build your career, try to identify your own superpowers." and by superpowers she means the 'personal power sources' above.

A project manager serves as the main resource for your team when it comes to communicating and clarifying goals, action items, progress, and updates.

Project document responsibility:

- how those documents get used,
- who has access to those documents,
- how often the documents get updated.

You'll need to communicate certain information to your team multiple times and in various ways.

- Some people learn by listening,
- some people learn by watching,
- and others learn by doing.

principles of **effective email writing** that will help your emails to stand out, be remembered, and elicit the response you need. These principles are:

- State what you want clearly. think about what you want, when you need what you want, and the best way to get what you want when you want it.
 - o Include your request in the subject line of your email.
 - o State your request within the first two paragraphs of your email message.
 - o Indicate the specific call-to-action associated with your request (for example, reply, review, RSVP).
 - o Write clear, concise sentences when providing details.
 - o Define terms. Avoid using acronyms and terminology that users may not know. Provide additional information as necessary to avoid misunderstanding.
- Keep the content short and concise. Make your words work for you.
 - o Summarize the content you want to convey, and remove anything in your email that doesn't contribute to your goal.
 - o Aim to write "question-less" and "self-standing" emails. This means that the message contains enough information to stand on its own. The reader shouldn't have any questions about what you want and when you want it.
 - o Know your audience. Some people—such as executives and other busy leadership—may not want to read emails of more than a few sentences or click on external links for further information. Try to tailor your emails accordingly.
- Structure your writing. Structure has to do with the visual flow, or aesthetics, of your email.
 - o **Use bullets.** Bullets break up the visual flow. If you have more than one of something, consider using bullets. Write strong action verbs at the start of each bullet.
 - o **Use labels.** Labels help guide the reader to what information is most important.
 - o **Add hyperlinks.** Hyperlinks allow readers to directly access additional information, rather than adding lengthy details to your email.
 - o **Write a strong topic sentence.** Place the main idea of the paragraph in the topic sentence.
- Check grammar, punctuation, and spelling.

E-mail best practices:

- carefully select who you're sending an email to and why.
- Make sure the subject field clearly states what the email is about.
- Keep your messages as short as possible and stay on topic.
- consider placing the information into a digital document you can link or attach to the email.
- Clearly state action items.
- Use correct grammar and spelling
- Write in an appropriate tone.

virtual meeting tools like Google Meet and Zoom are great for communicating.

there are work management and collaboration tools like Google Drive, Asana, and Smartsheet. These kinds of tools make it easier to share information among teams.

Meetings:

Effective meeting elements:

- Structured
 - o means they start and end on time.
 - o The attendees have been carefully selected.
 - o The meeting topics are prioritized.
 - o the designated note taker has been assigned.
- intentional
 - o they have a clearly stated purpose and expectations
 - **Your meeting's purpose**, or goal, describes the reason you're meeting and what you'd like to achieve.
 - send any pre-reading materials in advance of the meeting so that everyone shows up prepared to participate.
 - o everyone understands why they're attending.
- Collaborative: is when people work together to produce or create something.
 - o Be sure the agenda is clear about the objectives of the session.
 - o have a digital shared meeting document.
 - o it's important to respect and embrace each individual's preferred communication style.
 - o Let folks know they're welcome to respond.
- Inclusive: is the practice or policy of including people who might otherwise be excluded or marginalized.
 - o leave space in the meeting for participants who've been quiet.
 - o ensure that your meetings and presentations are accessible.

When planning your meetings, you should consider the needs of people experiencing the following types of disabilities:

- o **Visual impairments and blindness**
- o **Hearing loss and deafness**

- **Mobility disabilities**, which means having difficulty getting around, such as people who require wheelchairs or canes.

timeboxing, means you're setting a time limit for discussion. In a timebox, you give each topic a buffer of a few minutes to make sure you're not over packing your agenda.

consider appointing a meeting **moderator or facilitator**. This person will guide the meeting and help participants ask questions in real-time, while someone else is presenting. This way the presenter can stay focused on their topic while the moderator pays attention to the participants and can help guide participants on when they can chime in.

Productive meetings elements:

- Active participation from attendees.
- A clear and concise agenda that is followed throughout.
- The correct attendees (meaning the participants can contribute to achieving the meeting's goal).

Project management meetings types:

- project kick-off: This is often considered the official beginning of a project and serves as a way to align the team's understanding of the project goals with actual plans and procedures.
- status updates: This category includes regular team meetings where the primary goal is to align the team on updates, progress, challenges, and next steps. Status update topics such as:
 - task updates.
 - schedule status
 - budget status, any new items that impact your bottom line.
 - Discuss current or anticipated issues: changes, risks, resource issues, vendor issues, discuss action items
 - Factors to determine status meeting frequency:
 - the project's complexity,
 - number of team members,
 - the level of information required by the project sponsor, clients, or others.
- stakeholder reviews: The goal of a stakeholder meeting is to get buy-in and support. It reviews topics such as:
 - present a project update.
 - seek out and listen to feedback.
 - make a decision or resolve a major issue surrounding your project.
- project reviews. A typical retrospective meeting agenda
 - includes reviewing lessons learned what worked and what need to be improved.
 - Celebration.

Project closing: consists of the process performed to formally complete the project, the current phase, and contractual obligations.

An important thing to know: completing a project is not the same thing as closing a project.

There are three criteria that make up a project closing:

- assure all work is done: There's a chance one of your tasks may have been overlooked.
- Ensure that the agreed upon project management processes are executed: Sometimes, managerial tasks get overlooked, such as procedural or administrative work that needs to take place afterwards might slip your mind.
- get formal recognition from stakeholders that the project is done: because otherwise some of the stakeholders might think that the project is still active and request more tasks and then the team members will dedicate time and money for it. Which means a big waste.

To avoid negative impacts to your team, there are a couple of different types of projects that you'll want to avoid. These are:

- the **never-ending** project. exists when, the project deliverables and tasks cannot be completed.
- the **abandoned** project. exists when inadequate handoff of the project deliverables occurs.
-

Skipping steps in the project closing could result in:

- Impact the product's or service's scheduled launch dates.
- Put your organization at legal risk.
- Result in significant financial losses to your organization.
- Undermine your team's credibility, and yours.
- Damage your relationship with the customer or client.

a small closing process at the end of each milestone or a formal and more comprehensive closing phase near the very end.

conduct closing processes after each **phase or milestone**:

- refer to prior documentation such as:
 - o your statement of work.
 - o request for proposal.
 - o risk register.
 - o RACI chart.
- put together closing documentation:
 - o creating closeout reports
- conduct administrative closure of the procurement process.
 - o Close any contracts necessary,
 - o deliver the payments to vendors,
 - o retrieve all final deliverables from contracted workers.
- Make sure all stakeholders are aware that a phase or project is ending.
- complete any necessary follow-up work.

close at the very **end** of your project:

- provide the necessary training tools, documentation, and capabilities to use your product.

- ensure that the project has satisfied its goals and desired outcomes.
- document acceptance from all stakeholders.
- review all contracts and documentation.
- conduct a formal retrospective.
- disband and thank the project team.

Impact reporting is a presentation that's given at the end of a project for key stakeholders, which typically includes the stakeholders you had in the initial kick-off meeting.

The **purpose** of your impact report is to show your key stakeholders the impact your project had on the organization. Goals, objectives, budget, schedules, and key performance indicators (KPIs) need to be determined at the beginning of your project. demonstrate how well you did against those early targets.

Use metrics to showcase your results in an impact report:

- Improvement in schedule performance
- Revenue growth
- Positive return on investment (ROI)
- Increased external user counts
- Increased percentage of internal users
- Cost vs. margins
- High percentage of customer satisfaction
- Reduction in overhead
- Reduction in technical issues
- Time saved

Effective impact report:

- **Be concise.**
- **Understand your audience.**
- **Use visuals.**
- **Describe your learnings.**
- **Keep your stakeholders engaged.**
 - o **Show:** Play videos of demos, testimonials, or case studies.
 - o **Storytell:** Tell a story or anecdote related to the data in the report.
 - o **Engage:** Ask for audience participation through questions, surveys, or quizzes.

the three main **retrospective benefits** for your team:

- **encourage team-building** because they allow team members to understand differing perspectives.
- facilitate improved collaboration.
- they promote positive changes.

Project **closeout** report serves:

- it's a blueprint to document what the team did, how they did it, and what they delivered.
- provides an evaluation of the quality of work.
- it evaluates the project's performance with respect to budget and schedule.

Project **closeout** steps:

- Put together closing documentation
- Refer to prior documentation
- Complete any necessary follow-up work
- Make sure all stakeholders are aware that this phase is ending
- Conduct administrative closure of the procurement process

The closeout reports is created by project managers for project managers

Agile project management:

- **Waterfall:** refers to the sequential or linear ordering of phases.
- The term "agile" refers to:
 - o being able to move quickly and easily.
 - o flexibility and the willingness and ability to change and adapt.
- Agile's iterative **approach** enables the project to move quickly, as well as making it much more adaptive to change.
- **Agile project management** is an approach to project and team management based on the Agile Manifesto.
- The **manifesto** is a collection of four values and 12 principles that define the mindset that all Agile teams should strive for.
- Long story-short Waterfall is linear and sequential and does not encourage changing up the process once it is started. Agile, on the other hand, is iterative, flexible, and incorporates necessary changes throughout the process.
- In 2001, thought leaders and creators came together to find common ground between their methods and solve a problem. The problem, they agreed, was that companies were so focused on planning and documenting their projects they lost sight of what really mattered: Thought leaders and creators came together to help companies better please their customers.
- Agile was **created to**:
 - o To embrace the reality that the world is uncertain
 - o To act as a direct response to the strict linear processes of Waterfall
 - o To help project managers who work with unpredictability
- Agile aims for getting customer feedback more quickly to make sure that the team is building what the customer really wants.
- Part of working with an Agile mindset is always seeking out ways to work more efficiently. We do this by finding ways to streamline processes without reducing product quality or value.
- The key to streamlining is to reduce waste.
- **Aspects** of project:
 - o Requirements: are conditions that must be met or tasks that must be finished to ensure the successful completion of the project.

- Documentation:
- Deliverables: is a tangible outcome from a project.
- In a waterfall project **change control board**—a formal and rigorous process to manage any changes to requirements.

Waterfall	Agile
- need to have several formally approved project plans.	- requirements are treated as more dynamic and expected to change as the team receives feedback and new information.
- use lots of documentation because there are lots of handoffs between phases and handoffs among different teams within the project.	- instead of big, formal documents with a rigorous change management and approval process, there are shorter documents that have just enough detail to achieve their purpose.
- you often don't release the deliverable until the very end. The final product release feels like a big event.	- is just as exciting, but has smaller more frequent releases. So, each release has a less formal celebration, but it builds up to be just as exciting.

Agile values and principles inform the why, how, and what of Agile project management planning and processes. Let's take it from the top.

The Manifesto is saying that it's helpful for every Agile team to think about both sides of each statement during the execution of a project but should find ways to ensure that they're always placing more value and emphasis on the things on the left over the things on the right.

The Manifesto for Agile software development states:

“We are uncovering better ways of developing software by doing it and helping others do it. Through this work, we have come to value individuals and interactions over processes and tools, working software over comprehensive documentation, customer collaboration over contract negotiation, responding to change over following a plan. That is, while there is value in the items on the right, we value the items on the left more.”

The four **values of the agile** manifesto:

- the Manifesto emphasizes individuals and interactions over processes and tools. this value stresses people communicating with each other over using lots of processes and tools to force things to happen in a certain way.
- working software over comprehensive documentation, meaning that teams should prioritize spending time working on things that actually create value and avoid spending any more time than they really need on debating, writing, and reviewing documents.
- customer collaboration over contract negotiation. the customer's satisfaction is considered the highest priority of building a high quality and valuable product.
- responding to change over following a plan: every Agile team needs to acknowledge that change is inevitable. The larger or longer and more complex your project is, the more uncertainty there is.

The twelve principles of the agile manifesto are grouped into **four themes**, which is:

- Value delivery, or how do Agile teams deliver highly valuable products to their customers? This theme is about delivering the work as quickly as possible. So that we can get feedback and mitigate the risk that we spend too much time building the wrong thing.
- Business collaboration, or how do Agile teams collaborate with their business partners and stakeholders to create business value to the organization and their users? Collaborating with your customers helps the team get critical business information immediately by allowing them to adjust and adapt to any new information instantly.
- Team culture, or how does a team create and maintain the right interpersonal and team dynamics to deliver value for the customers and the business? creating an effective team culture that is inclusive, supportive, and empowering.
 - o to making sure your team is motivated to do the right thing,
 - o feels trusted to do the right thing,
 - o has the resources and space to work closely together on their goals,
 - o works at a sustainable pace.
- retrospectives, or how does the project learn to continuously increase performance of an organization and business? At regular intervals, the team reflects on how to become more effective, then tunes and adjusts its behavior accordingly.
 - o it is important for Agile teams to continuously learn and adapt to what's working and what's not working for them.

Questions for improvement:

- How is the team doing?
- Are the customers happy?
- Are there processes we could optimize?
- Are our tools working for us?
- Are we following the values?
- Are we accumulating any debt? And by "debt" I mean processes or technology that slows us down.

The 12 principles are:

- **“Our highest priority is to satisfy the customer through early and continuous delivery of valuable software.”**
- **“Welcome changing requirements, even late in development. Agile processes harness change for the customer’s competitive advantage.”**
- **“Deliver working software frequently, from a couple of weeks to a couple of months, with a preference to the shorter timescale.”**
- **“Business people and developers must work together daily throughout the project.”**
- **“Build projects around motivated individuals. Give them the environment and support they need, and trust them to get the job done.”**
- **“The most efficient and effective method of conveying information to and within a development is face-to-face conversation.”**
- **“Working software is the primary measure of progress.”**

- **“Agile processes promote sustainable development. The sponsors, developers, and users should be able to maintain a constant pace indefinitely.”**
 - **“Continuous attention to technical excellence and good design enhances agility.”**
 - **“Simplicity—the art of maximizing the amount of work not done—is essential.”**
 - **“The best architectures, requirements, and designs emerge from self-organizing teams.”**
 - **“At regular intervals, the team reflects on how to become more effective, then tunes and adjusts its behavior accordingly.”**
-
- ★ Simplicity allows a team to focus and work on the things that matter the most.
 - ★ "business people" to refer to those involved with things like sales, marketing, customer support, and account management. We'll use the term "developers" to refer to those who are involved with making and creating products.

Remember, Agile is about delivering value in a world with high degrees of uncertainty, risk, and competition.

Agile works best in industries or projects that are susceptible to or that encourage change and uncertainty.

VUCA is an acronym that defines the conditions that affect organizations in a changing and complex world.

VUCA stands for volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity.

Volatility refers to the rate of change and churn in a business or situation.

Uncertainty refers to the lack of predictability or high potential for surprise.

Complexity refers to the high number of interrelated forces, issues, organizations, and factors that would influence the project.

Ambiguity refers to the possibility of misunderstanding the conditions and root causes of events or circumstances.

When using VUCA:

- examine the environment and conditions in which the project exists before we decide the best approach to use.
- If your project environment has high levels of volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity, then it's a good sign that you should consider an Agile approach.
- While an Agile approach is not a perfect solution that will get rid of VUCA, it will lead to better outcomes by giving you and your team tools and systems to mitigate the risks that VUCA presents.

SCRUM:

- **Scrum** refers to a formation in rugby where all of the players on the team lean forward, lock their heads together, and then work as one unit to try and gain precious yards towards the scoring line.
- When you **use Scrum for project management**, you form a team that will work together to quickly develop and test a deliverable. The work is completed in short cycles, and the team meets daily to discuss current tasks and clear up anything that's blocking their progress.
- The product **Backlog** is the central artifact in Scrum, where all possible ideas, deliverables, features, or tasks are captured for the team to work on.
- The **Sprint** is the name of the time-boxed period in Scrum where work is done. This Sprint can be between one and four weeks long, but most Sprints are around two weeks. This is often called the "**iteration.**"
- **Daily Scrum**, also called the Stand-up. This is where the team meets for 15 minutes or less every day of the Sprint to inspect their progress. toward their goal.
- Roles in **SCRUM**:
 - o **Scrum Master**. This role is responsible for ensuring that the team lives Agile values and principles, follows the processes and practices that the team agreed to, sharing information to the larger project team, and they also help the team focus on doing their best work.
 - o **Product Owner**, who is responsible for maximizing the value of the product and the work of the team.
 - o **Development Team**: is responsible for how a team will deliver that product.

SCRUM **popularity** reasons:

- it has clear roles and responsibilities for the folks on the team while continuously emphasizing the power of the team.
- Scrum has very regular and predictable meetings and delivery schedules with predefined agendas and outcomes for the meetings.
- It supports and reinforces the Agile values and principles while adding some structure and foundations that help new Agile teams get started and more experienced teams get better.
- free and open for all to use. Since it's the most commonly-used Agile delivery framework, there's also a huge amount of guidance and support online, as well as Scrum-specific training and certifications.

Scrum is **ideal** for the following:

- a Scrum team should be cross-functional, with around three to nine team members. Some call this a "pizza-size team" because it has the same amount of people who could share a large pizza.
- Scrum works best for projects where the team and management are open-minded, adaptable, and value continuously learning how to be a better team.

characteristics of a team help to move the Scrum downfield:

- **Built-in instability**, this gives teams “an element of tension” necessary to “carry out a project of strategic importance to the company.”

- **Self-organizing teams:** Scrum Teams were intended to operate like their own start-up, with a unique order that lacks true hierarchy.
- **Overlapping development phases:** Individuals on a Scrum Team must “work toward synchronizing their pace to meet deadlines.”
- **Multi-learning:** Scrum is a framework that relies heavily on trial and error.
- **Subtle control:** By creating checkpoints throughout the project to analyze team interactions and progress, Scrum Teams maintain control without hindering creativity.
- **Organizational transfer of learning:** On Scrum Teams, everyone is encouraged to learn skills that may be new to them as they support other team members.

The **Kanban name** comes from two Japanese words. "Kan" meaning "sign," and "ban" meaning "board."

The reason Kanban is so **popular** is that

- it provides transparent visual feedback.
- ensures that the project team only accepts a sustainable amount of in progress work.

the **work-in- progress limit**, or **WIP limit** means the amount of in progress tasks are limited to what the team can handle during a certain amount of time.

flow is a core principle of Kanban. trying to maximize efficiency by focusing on less work, the work gets done faster.

Extreme Programming or XP:

It was **named** that because it took traditional software development activities to an extreme level. And it also emerged at the same time as extreme sports like snowboarding.

The XP methodology **aims** to improve product quality and the ability to respond to changing customer needs. It does this by taking best practices for the development process to extreme levels.

XP activities:

- **Designing:** in software development, this is where you write a design document describing the parts of the code or instructions for the product and how it will function. In non-software environments. This would be describing the various pieces and parts for whatever it is you're trying to deliver.
 - XP wants to ensure that all of the pieces of the product will fit together properly. So it stresses **simplicity**.
- **Coding:** XP demands clear and concise code, so that others can easily read and understand the program.
- **Testing:** In XP, more is better. So, if a little bit of testing can eliminate a few flaws, lots of testing will eliminate even more. The goal is to test for and eliminate any flaws in a feature before building it and continuing on.
- **Listening:** to the customer and ensuring that the requirements are integrated into the product.

XP innovative practices:

- **pair programming**, which is when two team members Work together at the same time on one task.
- **continuous integration and continuous refactoring**. This is the practice of merging product changes into a shared version several times a day in order to get quick feedback on the quality of the code or product.
- **avoid big design up front**. This relates to designing and means the design should be just enough to get started and should be continuously improved as the product evolves.
- **write tests, not requirements**. This means that instead of writing a product requirements document and then later writing a test plan. Your test plan can serve two purposes by A. telling the team what to build, and B. comparing what they built to what was supposed to be built.

Lean 6-sigma:

Lean methodology consists of five principles that serve as a recipe for improving project outcomes.

- define value, identifying and focusing on what the customer wants and including the customer in the process.
- map value stream, means mapping out the process or stream, including all the steps involved in producing value for the customer.
- create flow, means ensuring the product flows through the value stream efficiently, continuing to eliminate waste throughout the cycle.
- establish pull, think of asking someone to pull something off the shelf. You want to make sure the customer is pulling on the product or asking for it throughout the value stream. They might pull or ask for features and incremental deliveries.
- pursue perfection, this means pushing your team to continuously improve the first four process steps.

the **real power of Agile** comes from not only adopting certain processes or strategies but also from adopting a certain kind of mindset—one that is necessarily different from the traditional Waterfall models.

Reasons to blend waterfall and agile:

- Your stakeholders, customers, or sponsors are more comfortable with traditional approaches and using workflows, or delivering traditional work products is easier for them to understand and follow, but your project team is already established in Scrum and they wish to continue.
- regulatory requirements that insist on certain traditional work processes.
- the vendors involved in a large project is already following a traditional approach and the integration between the teams require some blending of methods.

The Spotify model:

- encourages innovation, collaboration, and productivity while maintaining autonomy, quality, and necessary communication. It does so by using a unique organization system that features Squads, Tribes, Chapters, and Guilds.
 - o **Squads.** A Squad is like a Scrum Team and is supposed to feel like its own start-up within the company. Squads are self-organizing and collocated. They work together to achieve a long-term mission.
 - o **Tribes** are collections of squads that work in a specific area and are meant to have less than 100 people.
 - o **Chapters** are small groups of people across a tribe that have similar skills and work in the same general competency area.
 - o **Guilds** are the largest group, comprised of people across the organization who want to share knowledge, tools, code, and practices.
- Takeaways from Spotify model:
 - o **You must always be able to adapt based on your team's preferences and goals.** The Spotify team started in Squads, but as they scaled, they added new types of groups within the organization—without disrupting the existing Squads. They continued to do so until they found the perfect balance of collaboration and ownership.
 - o **Always examine the needs of your project and organization.** What works for Spotify may not be an exact fit for your team. If you are on a team that needs scaling, be inspired by this model, but use the aspects that work best for your organization.
 - o **Don't be afraid of trial and error.** If you try something and it doesn't feel quite right, you can easily adjust.
 - o **You should never consider yourself done improving.** There are always changes that can be made for the better.

The Scrum Guide, is a main source of truth for Scrum Teams and is available for free at [Scrumguides.org](https://www.scrumguides.org).

Agile is the foundational philosophy and mindset, while Scrum is a framework that materializes or brings that philosophy to life.

Scrum theory: - three pillars

- five values

Scrum Team: the Product Owner,

Scrum Master,

the Development Team.

The scrum guide defines **Scrum** as a framework for developing, delivering, and sustaining complex products.

Iterative refers to the fact that project processes are repeated.

Incremental refers to the work being divided into smaller chunks that build on each other.

Empiricism: that true knowledge comes from actual, lived experience.

Empiricism is built on three foundational **pillars**. Those pillars are **transparency, inspection, and adaptation**, and they're also the three pillars of Scrum.

Transparency means that we make the most significant aspects of our work visible to those responsible for the outcome. Transparency inside a Scrum Team is critical to the team's productivity and the project's completion.

Inspection refers to conducting timely checks towards the outcome of a Sprint goal to detect undesirable variances.

The more inspections that take place, the more improvement a team experiences in their work.

Adaptation means that we're continuously searching for ways to adjust our project, product, or processes to minimize any further deviation or issues.

Scrum Teams work and behave according to five **core values**:

- **Commitment:** This means personally committing to achieving the goals of the Scrum Team.
- **Courage:** Scrum Team members must have the courage to do the right thing and work on tough problems.
- **Focus:** refers to everyone focusing on the necessary work within the Sprint and the overall goals of the Scrum Team.
- **Openness:** the team and its stakeholders agree to be open about all the work and the various challenges that come with performing the work.
- **Respect:** Team members should respect the opinions, skills, and independence of their teammates.

For a team to bring the three pillars of Scrum **to life**, they must act in accordance with the five Scrum values.

Scrum is an agile methodology and keeping that in mind, **One of the Agile principles** states: Build projects around motivated individuals. Give them the environment and support they need and trust them to get the job done.

In Agile, a **mission** is a short statement that stays constant for your team throughout the process and gives them something to work toward.

product vision making it clear what outcomes the team is responsible for and where your team's boundaries are.

A mission tells me why we're doing the work. A product vision helps me imagine what the work will be like when we're done.

Every **Scrum Team** consists of three defined roles: a Scrum Master, a Product Owner, and the Development Team:

- **The Product Owner** is responsible for what a team builds. They also must ensure everyone understands the why.
- **The Development Team** is responsible for how a team will deliver that product.
- **The Scrum Master** is responsible for when a team will deliver value to its users. This role is roughly equivalent to the project manager role in traditional projects.

Scrum Teams must exhibit a few **specific skills**,

- Scrum Teams are cross-functional. When a Scrum Team delivers something, it's the accomplishment of the entire team, no matter what function or organization they're in.
- Scrum Teams are self-organizing, (self-managing)

The Scrum Master promotes and supports the Scrum process by helping everyone understand and implement Scrum.

The Scrum Master's responsibilities include:

- coaching team members on the Agile and Scrum practices, rules, and values.
- helping to find ways to manage the Product Backlog effectively.
- Causing the removal of impediments to the Scrum Team's progress
- Ensuring that all Scrum events take place and are positive, productive, and kept within the **timebox** (a Scrum concept that refers to the estimated duration for an event)

The Product Backlog is the single authoritative source for things that a team works on. It contains:

- all of the product features,
- product requirements,
- activities associated with deliverables

The scrum master is **responsible for**:

- facilitates Scrum events such as Sprint Retrospectives
- helps the team remove any blockers to their progress
- prevents unhelpful interactions or interruptions coming from outside of the team.

Scrum Masters **must have**:

- good organizational skills
- be supportive leaders
- facilitate productivity and collaboration.
- coach team members on Scrum theory and application.
- great communicators

The **product owner** is **responsible for**:

- continuously maximizing the value of the product delivered by the Scrum Team.
- helping the Scrum Team understand why their work matters within the overall goal and mission.
- They also prioritize the Product Backlog to optimize the delivery of goals and deliver value to customers.
- ensures that the Product Backlog is visible and transparent to all.
- making sure that the product or service fulfills the customer's needs.

Product owners' skills:

- Customer-focused.
- Decisive.
- Flexible.
- Optimistic and positive.
- Available
- Collaborative

The Development Team is made up of the people who do the work to build the product. The size of the team ranges from three to nine people.

Traits of the development team:

- Cross functional.
- Self-organizing
- Supportive
- Customer oriented

Responsibilities of the product team:

- Creating a plan for the Sprint, the **Sprint Backlog** (the set of Product Backlog items that are selected to be completed during the upcoming Sprint).
- Instilling quality by adhering to a Definition of Done.
- Adapting their plan each day toward the Sprint Goal.
- Holding each other accountable as professionals.
- Executing sprints by designing, building, and testing Product Backlog items in increments.

A **timebox** is a Scrum concept that refers to the estimated duration for an event.

The difference between the scrum master and the project manager roles:

A **Scrum Master** is responsible for helping the team understand Scrum theory and practice. They ensure Scrum events take place and help the team focus on delivering value by removing impediments. But unlike a **traditional project manager**, they do not take on the management of changes in scope or priorities. Additionally, Scrum Masters do not maintain traditional project artifacts like Gantt charts.

Differences and similarities between project management and a project owner:

- In traditional project management, scope management is the primary responsibility of the project manager. But in Scrum, the definition and management of product scope falls to the Product Owner. Conversely, the Product Owner isn't responsible for team performance—they aren't considered to be a manager.
- both roles are tasked with stakeholder management.

in many companies—including Google—the definition of product or solution scope is the responsibility of a separate role called a **product manager**. So, it is important to understand the place you are working in.

Product Backlog is the single authoritative source for things that a team works on. It contains all the features, requirements, and activities associated with deliverables to achieve the goal of the project.

Three **key features** of the product back log:

- a **living artifact**, meaning that items are added to the Backlog at any time.
- owned and adjusted by the product owner
- always a prioritized list of features.

Best practices and pieces of data when working with backlog:

- the description: it describes an item. be clear when adding Product Backlog items so the details are encouraged.
- the value: tells us how much business value the item delivers to the customers, to the team, or to the users.
- the order: Backlogs order items from highest to lowest priority. This is called a stacked rank.
- the estimate: An estimate is how much effort the Scrum Team thinks an item will take to complete.

User stories are short, simple descriptions of a feature told from the perspective of the user.

User stories are made up of three different elements:

- the user,
- the action they will take,
- the benefit to them.

The most common format for a user story is: "As a user role, I want this action so that I can get this value."

Each user story should meet six different criteria, (**INVEST**):

- I, for independent: the story should be able to be started and finished by itself.
- The N stands for negotiable: there's room for negotiation and discussion about this item.
- The V is for valuable: this means that completing the user story has to deliver value.
- E is for estimable: our Definition of Done must be clear so that the team can give each user story an estimate.
- The S is for small: each user story needs to be able to fit within a planned Sprint.
- the T is testable: a test can be written to check and make sure that it meets the acceptance criteria.

Purpose of the user story: User stories are concise, specific descriptions of a feature told from the user's perspective. They allow the team to create solutions centered on the user experience and help project managers capture and manage the Product Backlog.

Epic: means a group or collection of user stories.

acceptance criteria: which is essentially the checklist you will use to decide whether the user story is done.

User stories **include** the following:

- **User persona.** What is your user like? What is their relation to the project? What goals do they have?
- **Definition of Done.** This refers to an agreed upon set of items that must be completed before a user story can be considered complete.
- **Tasks.** What are the key activities needed to complete the user story?
- **Any feedback already provided.** If you are adding features to an existing product and you have already received feedback from customers on a past iteration, make sure to consider this feedback.

Work management tools like Asana are designed to reduce wasted time by empowering project managers to focus on project planning, team alignment, and resource allocation.

To create a backlog, create a new project by sprint planning template.

Most teams make projects at the beginning of each Sprint and then track their work through each stage, to make sure they know where their Sprint work stands.

Backlog refinement refers to the act of keeping the Backlog described, estimated and prioritized, so that the scrum team can operate effectively.

Purpose of reviewing the product backlog:

- it contains the appropriate items and that nothing new is needed or nothing needs to be removed.
- that the items are prioritized by the Product Owner, (this is also called setting the order field).
- that the items at the top of the Backlog are ready for delivery with clear acceptance criteria.
- that the Backlog items include estimates, or an informed assessment about how much work a particular Backlog item will be.

Through estimation, we can find out how much work we have ahead of us.

Relative estimation means that instead of trying to determine exactly how long a task will take, we compare the effort of that task, to the effort for another task, and that becomes the estimate.

two common relative estimation **methods**:

- **T-shirt sizes**: the team simply picks one item on the Backlog that seems to be about a medium size workload, and simply calls that a "medium" in the estimate field. After that they take another item on the Backlog and compare it to the medium item they just identified, and answer the question: if that first item was a medium, what size would I give this one? The team will repeat this process on each additional item.
- **story points**: (the better one) Most teams use a famous mathematical sequence of numbers called the Fibonacci sequence. The sequence is 0,1,1,2,3,5,8,13,21 continues to infinity. For the sake of story points, we skip zero and the first 1. These numbers are special in that they start out close to one another, but as the numbers get higher, they spread farther and farther out. This is helpful because as the estimate gets higher, the uncertainty and risk also get higher. This number combines both effort and risk into one number. In other words, there's not much use in debating estimation values between 21 and 25 points but choosing between 21 and 34 is a real conversation.

it's up to the team to decide when and how often to conduct Backlog refinement.

Agile estimation techniques:

- Planning Poker™: commonly used when Scrum teams have to make effort estimates for a small number of items (under 10). Planning Poker is consensus-based, meaning that everyone has to agree on the number chosen.
- Dot Voting: Dot Voting, like Planning Poker, is also good for sprints with a low number of Sprint Backlog items.
- The Bucket System: The Bucket System is helpful for backlogs with many items since it can be done very quickly. In fact, a couple hundred items can be estimated in just one hour with the Bucket System.
- Large/Uncertain/Small: is another quick method of rough estimation. It is great for product backlogs that have several similar or comparable items.
- Ordering Method: is ideal for projects with a smaller team and a large number of Product Backlog items.
- Affinity Mapping: is useful for teams that have more than 20 items in their Product Backlog.

Characteristics of effective estimation:

- **Avoids gathering false precision of estimates.** In Scrum, assigning rough estimates results in more accuracy across the project.
- **Avoids anchoring bias**: where anchoring bias is a known phenomenon, where individuals find themselves compelled to put forth estimates similar to others in the room to avoid embarrassment.
- **Promotes inclusivity.** These group estimation techniques not only lead to better estimates but also help the team develop trust and cohesiveness.
- **Leads to effort discovery.** Estimating in these dynamic ways can help the team uncover strategies to get items completed which might otherwise not have been revealed.

Some **best practices**, regardless of the technique you use, include:

- Asking the Product Owner questions about the user story or item to ensure that there is enough information to estimate it.
- Discussing divergent estimates from various team members so that everyone has a chance to understand how to implement the item.
- Agreeing on the final T-shirt sizes or points value and capturing it in the system.
- If certain items fall into the larger T-shirt size or story points value range, discussing whether it makes sense to break them down into smaller pieces before moving on.

Within a Sprint, the amount of work is planned based on the historical capacity of the team and is made ready for the Sprint Planning event.

The Scrum Guide technically defines **five events**:

- the Sprint itself,
- Sprint Planning,
- Daily Scrum,
- Sprint Review,
- the Sprint Retrospective.

Timeboxes benefits are that they:

- create a sense of urgency which will drive prioritization,
- provide a window of focus which improves productivity,
- they help the team develop a predictable rhythm to their work.

How to choose the **time a sprint takes**:

- think about what you expect the frequency of changes to be.
- think about how much focus time your solution developers might need to build a Backlog item.
- think about how much overhead goes into a delivery of your product.

A typical sprint takes Between one and four weeks.

During the Sprint:

- No changes are made that would endanger the Sprint Goal;
- Quality does not decrease;
- The Product Backlog is refined as needed; and,
- Scope may be clarified and renegotiated with the Product Owner as more is learned.

Sprint Planning, the entire Scrum team comes together and meets to confirm how much capacity, meaning time and people, are available during this Sprint. This becomes the Sprint Backlog, and ultimately, the Sprint goal.

Definition of Done: refers to an agreed upon set of items that must be completed before our user story or Backlog item can be considered complete.

Things might be **within** the definition of done:

- the code or solution itself is reviewed by an independent peer group.
- The product or unit passes all testing requirements, which could include security or performance testing.
- Documentation is completed.
- All user story acceptance criteria specified by the product owner is met.
- And finally, the product owner accepts the user story.

The Sprint Backlog is the set of product Backlog items that are identified for completion during the upcoming Sprint.

The daily scrum (stand up): is a time for the Scrum Team to synchronize and prioritize activities for the day.

The official Scrum Guide says that Daily Stand-ups must happen **every single day**,

the Sprint Review. This Sprint event is crucial to the Scrum Pillars of inspection and adaptation, and demonstrates the values of openness, courage, and respect.

The Sprint Review is a meeting with the entire Scrum Team where the product is demonstrated in order to determine which aspects are finished and which aren't.

The sprint review cover:

- exploration of which items should be considered done in the Product Backlog.
- demonstrate and inspect the product.

During the sprint review the team could work on:

- First, it makes the feedback as immediate as possible.
- Second, everyone has a voice
- the team learns more about how their marketing teammate does their job, leading to greater trust and understanding between team members.

The Product Increment is what's produced after a given Sprint.

Releasable (product): when the team has developed a Minimum Viable Product, which has a set of implemented features or requirements.

Minimum Viable Product is a version of a product with just enough features to satisfy early customers.

The Sprint Retrospective is an essential meeting of up to three hours for the Scrum Team to take a step back, reflect, and identify improvements about how to work together as a team.

During the sprint retrospective the Scrum Team will reflect on what's working or not working for the team regarding the people, the processes, and the tools:

- What improvements are worth exploring in the next Sprint?
- What improvements were put in place for the last Sprint?
- Were they helpful or not, and why?

Measures for a successful retrospective:

- Blameless
 - o You'll need to create a safe space for candor by acknowledging potential awkwardness and, if needed, create a space for anonymous or private feedback.
- Participation is key
 - o retrospectives only work if participants feel like their input matters.
- balance the negative with the positive.
 - o Don't just ask where you can improve, but also ask things like, where did we notice success?
- Act on it.
 - o Search for improvements, or simply convert the things that worked best into your team's habits and norms.

Pitfalls to avoid in retrospectives:

- **Avoid too many gimmicks.**
- **Try not to only focus on the negative.**
- **Avoid changing processes after each retrospective.**

Best practices in retrospectives:

- Ask open-ended, probing questions.
- Consider diverse styles of communication and participation.
- Cover the many aspects of the Sprint when conducting a retrospective.
 - o The productivity and efficiency of the team
 - o The scope and understanding of the definition of done
 - o Communication and interactions within the team
 - o Stakeholder communication
 - o Progress towards more long-range release plans
- Consider reflecting periodically on Scrum theory and values by asking specific questions.

burndown chart measures time against the amount of work done and the amount of work remaining. In a Scrum Team, burndown charts reflect how the team is doing with completing user stories during the Sprint.

velocity is a measure of how many points a team burns down during a single Sprint on average.

things worth **noting** when calculating velocity:

- there's no such thing as a good velocity or bad velocity. Velocity is simply what the team has historically been able to achieve in a predetermined timebox.

- each team will have a different velocity, especially since each team decides their own point system calibration.

Once you have a stable velocity and a refined Backlog with prioritization and estimates, you can now tell your stakeholders and sponsors:

- how long it will take to complete the entire Product Backlog.
- how much of your Backlog will be completed by a particular time.

Three **main features** make Kanban boards a great tool for scrum teams:

- Visualization.
- work-in-progress limits (also known as WIP limits).
- flow of work.

WIP limits are constraints on how many work items the team actively works on at any given time.

In scrum there is no multitasking, means the more work you have the less efficient you will become.

Types of transparency tools:

- documentation or word processing tool. ensures that you capture key information about your project in a long format.
- Spreadsheets.
- Presentations.

Types of collaboration tools:

- video conferencing,
- team and one-on-one online chats
- e-mails

The term "value" can mean different things for each customer based on what they expect the product to accomplish. could be:

- financial benefits.
- user growth and engagement.
- compliance adherence.

The term "**value-driven delivery**" means you and your team are focused on delivering a product of high value.

To keep the team focused on value-driven delivery:

- Build the right thing.
 - o make sure you really understand what your customers want.
- build the thing right.
 - o ensuring that your team only builds the requested or approved features.

- run it right.
 - o your team has thought through how the user will interact with the product once it's been delivered.

When reading **case studies**, focus on the problem, the effect it had on the business or organization, and the pros and cons of the solutions reached to help you determine some applicable key takeaways.

As you read, ask yourself:

- What is the issue?
- What is the goal of the analysis?
- What is the context of the problem?
- What key facts should be considered?
- What alternatives are available to the decision-maker?
- What would you recommend, and why?

value roadmap:

- It's an Agile way of mapping out the timelines and requirements for the product development process.
- can be used in all types of businesses.
- This roadmap is a guide that demonstrates (where to go, how to get there, and what to accomplish along the way) in order to maximize value.
- helps the team explain the vision of the product
- be used to identify important milestones.

A typical value roadmap has three **components**:

- a product vision,
- a product roadmap
- release plans.

The **product vision** defines:

- what the product is,
- how it supports the customer's business strategy,
- who will use it.

the **product roadmap**, which the Product Owner is responsible for creating and maintaining. It's key to making sure your team is building the right thing.

- It provides a high-level view of the expected product, its requirements.
- an estimated schedule for reaching milestones.

A **release plan** contains a

- **release goal**, which is an overall business goal for the features you plan to include in the release.
- the **list of Backlog items** such as epics, user stories, or features that you require for that release goal.
- an **estimated release date**.
- other **relevant dates** that impact a release, like a convention or major holiday.

Roadmaps may have many different names but all refers to the same thing:

- Project roadmap
- Product roadmap
- Value roadmap
- Lean roadmap
- Agile roadmap

benefits of developing and maintaining a value roadmap:

- Clarifying the sequence of deliverables.
- Showing teams how their efforts relate to the north-star vision. In other words, their ultimate goal.
- Showing stakeholders, the incremental value that will be achieved over the course of the project (rather than reviewing it as one big delivery at the end).
- Helping stakeholders roughly understand the layout of the work behind the deliverable.

pitfalls around value roadmaps to avoid:

- Letting stakeholders think the roadmap is set and unchangeable. This may cause stakeholders to impede teams' ability to adapt in response to new information, as well as put a lot of pressure on teams to achieve deadlines no matter what it takes.
- Spending too much time fine-tuning delivery dates versus keeping them rough and improving specificity as the dates get closer
- Putting all the work into creating the roadmap rather than producing the deliverables

best practices to get the most from value roadmaps:

- Make it highly noticeable to the team and refer to it frequently.
- Clearly indicate the highest priority items.
- If possible, clearly indicate the highest value items.
- Make it visible to your wider stakeholder group so that they can use it for their planning.
- Conduct regular reviews of the roadmap with sponsors, stakeholders, and the team to ensure that it is still providing the blueprint for the project.

Tips for creating a release plan:

- the Product Owner and Project Manager or Scrum Master work together to develop each release plan.

- release plans need to connect the product roadmap with the team's capacity and velocity.

The **capacity and velocity**: is the measure of the team's ability to complete work at a certain pace.

- Factor in any “hard” dates or deadlines.
- the Scrum Master or Project Manager should always review the release plan before starting a Sprint planning session.

Common **factors** may result in a change in the release plan:

- Team velocity change.
- Change to product scope.
- improving the understanding of how much effort is needed to build certain features.

The best way to think about changing your release plan:

- **Identifying a needed change:** first know what needs change, which one of the three constraints (scope, time, budget) or (what, when, how),
- **Deciding to make the change:** There are many decision-making models, most of them include:
 - o **Identify the “decider.”** have a single person to ensure consistency and accountability. generally, the Product Owner or a senior stakeholder
 - o **Develop and share what factors are important to the decision**, and gather supporting data that will help the decider make the decision.
 - o **Openly discuss the benefits and costs of the decision.** Identify areas of uncertainty and capture assumptions.
 - o **Document the decision.**
- **Implementing the change:**
 - o Document the change and decision-making process.
 - o Capture the change in any affected artifacts.
 - o Share the change with all affected stakeholders.
 - o Monitor the change for a certain amount of time.

As a beginner project manager, you probably will not be asked by a large organization to lead their **change to agile**, maybe by a small organization, and if you have to change the whole organization's management to agile it might need a cultural change which could take many years to do. So understanding “change management” might help.

Words of wisdom "Change takes patient persistence."

One way to lead change is to create a **sense of ownership**:

- find an executive sponsor who also feels a sense of ownership for the change you're creating.
- Having buy-in from someone at the top increases your chances of successfully driving any change in organizational culture.

- Connect the change to the company’s mission or values.

Another way to lead change is to create a **sense of urgency**:

- ask the team, the organization, and the stakeholders questions about what's working and what's not working right now.
 - o What is preventing us from providing the best possible product to our customers?
 - o What is allowing our competitors to outperform us in this market?
 - o How can we help our teams become more productive and supported in their work?

Being an **influencer**, it is about someone’s ability to lead and influence others to change their behaviors, hearts, and minds to produce meaningful, sustainable results, not getting likes on social media.

In order **to have** real influence, you need others to trust you, consider you an authority, and have confidence in your decisions.

The **three keys** to influence are:

- **Clarify measurable results:** You can’t influence others to change until you know what you want, why you want it, and when you want it.
- **Find vital behaviors:** A **vital behavior** is the action an individual takes at a pivotal moment in the context of the change they are seeking.
- **Use the six sources of influence:** six sources or factors that were correlated with successful change,
 - o **Personal motivation:** *Example:* Ensure the Product Owner is timely, appreciative, and effective while giving their feedback.
 - o **Personal ability:** *Example:* Ensure that the developer knows how to use the available demo tools and can easily send a quick video of the new feature in their email to the Product Owner.
 - o **Social motivation:** *Example:* Have the Development Team members remind each other in the Daily Scrum to email the Product Owner before they finalize the work.
 - o **Social ability:** *Example:* Give the Development Team a tool to track all of their demos to the Product Owner during the Sprint.
 - o **Structural motivation:** *Example:* Provide a coffee gift card Sprint award that the Product Owner gets to award after each Sprint.
 - o **Structural ability:** *Example:* Add a rule to the content management system that pre-populates the name of the Product Owner in the reviewer list.

Influence	Persuasion
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges involve changing long-term, deeply entrenched behaviors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges are more short-term.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Getting support is often many people and many interlocked behaviors. - Challenges require changing minds, hearts, and actions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges typically involve getting someone to say yes or no. - Challenges are about getting verbal agreement or support.
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Being an **agile coach** means:

- **You'll design the sprint with the team:** The playbook should include how the whole team runs a Sprint Review, how the team works day-to-day, and how the team publishes plans to stakeholders.
- **You'll provide feedback to the team:** Providing feedback shouldn't only be about fixing broken things but finding processes and activities that worked well and encourage the team to continue using the things that work.
- **You'll celebrate and learn with the team:** Congratulate the team often on a job well done, a happy customer, or a big solution launch. If the team "loses," meaning they weren't successful in fulfilling a requirement, acknowledge that loss as critical data that will help the team improve next time.

Management differs from coaching: Management is about giving direction, while coaching is about teaching. The main difference between coaching and management is communication.

In management managers streamline communication and give directions, managing requires overseeing the work of others and can include:

- Onboarding and orienting new employees
- Conducting meetings
- Delegating tasks and assignments
- Monitoring progress and performance against those tasks
- Making high-level decisions

In coaching When challenges arise, coaches will offer guidance, then get out of the way, Coaching is about building confidence and capabilities so that individuals can continuously grow and improve. There are a few principles to keep in mind when coaching:

- **Motivate:** coaches point out the value in others' work and instill within them a sense of pride in what they do.
- **Support:** Coaches are an accessible resource for their team to come to when they experience problems or if they have an idea, they want their feedback on.
- **Encourage and appreciate:** When someone on their team is struggling with a heavy workload, a coach will acknowledge and validate the weight of their efforts and assure them that they can handle the challenges ahead.

the **four themes of Agile** principles:

- value delivery,
- business collaboration,
- team dynamics,
- culture and retrospectives.

value delivery, is about making sure the team is delivering working solutions frequently.

signs of **value delivery issues**, things like:

- missing expected delivery dates and
- burned out,
- too many items in progress.

Solution to value delivery issues:

- more demos of the solutions.
- use retrospectives, to ask the team if anything is slowing them down
- make sure that everyone understands what "done" means.
- be sure to focus on only a few user stories per Sprint.

business collaboration is about making sure that developers are collaborating with business people on how to build the right product.

Signs of **business collaboration issues:**

- You might notice that the team is overwhelmed with critical feedback or change requests, that may lead for people on the team to stop asking for feedback or start complaining.
- "us versus them" mentality between the team doing the work and management.

Solutions to business collaboration issues:

- address critical feedback and change requests by doing more demos.
- conducting a Solution Design Sprint.
- ensuring changes to the Backlog are introduced only in between Sprints.

dynamics and culture. is about how human beings are complex creatures with lots of different motivations and styles of working.

Signs of team **dynamics and culture issues:**

- low team morale.
- Lots of conflict
- Low conflict: if a team never has disagreements, it's a sign that they might be worried about starting a conflict because they don't feel like it's a safe environment.

Solutions to team dynamics and culture issues:

- run a team brainstorm session
- change up the workflows.
- take a training class together

One of the retrospective techniques is called the **Six Hats Thinking Technique**. In this technique, each team member chooses a different hat to explore the subject of the retrospective. The different hats each involve a different objective, like discussing positives or negatives that happened during the Sprint or sharing emotive statements.

Common coaching challenges:

- managing a stable product roadmap,
- incomplete implementation of Scrum,
- experiencing a lack of stability within the team.

main causes of an unstable product roadmap:

- product ambition.
 - o Product ambition poses a challenge when product leadership is overly ambitious about what the team can realistically deliver.
 - Product ambition solution:
 - agree up front how to handle new opportunities,
 - set up regular roadmap reviews with the entire team
 - promote sharing knowledge between the Product Owner and the Development Team
- product assumptions.
 - o too many assumptions can jeopardize the team's success.
 - Product assumptions solutions:
 - Document the assumptions and make them transparent.
 - Check assumption against unbiased user research.

Unbiased user research:

- gathers information about what users really want.
- It allows you to confirm or reject assumptions
- helps you move forward with confidence.

Incomplete implementation of scrum issues:

- loss of clear roles and responsibilities.
- tempted to skip some events or blend them to save time.
- not providing the team with the Scrum coaching they need.

Solutions to incomplete implementation of scrum:

- implement Scrum completely.
- make sure roles are well-defined and properly fulfilled.

Lack of team stability **issues**:

- Changes in team composition.

Lack of team stability solutions:

- have a quick onboarding process
- Use pair programming style
- Have shorter sprints.

Google Cloud Platform Business **defines DevOps** as an organizational and cultural movement that aims to increase software delivery velocity, improve service reliability, and build shared ownership among software stakeholders.

DevOps **is about** growing and managing teams and organizations that can build and evolve large-scale systems at a rapid pace. These systems need to be both secure and reliable, so they can better deliver value to customers and organizations.

business agility, means incorporating Agile principles into the wide sphere of management. This helps organizations facing VUCA conditions such as volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity.

DevOps are process and tools focused, **while agile** is people-centric focused.

Five frameworks that **scale** the agile approach:

- **Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe):** is a Lean-Agile scaling framework that draws heavily on concepts from Kanban, Scrum, Extreme Programming (XP), DevOps, and Design Thinking methodologies.
 - o **Alignment:** Synchronize the planning and execution of SAFe activities at all levels of the organization.
 - o **Built-in Quality:** Build quality into all stages of solution development.
 - o **Transparency:** Make execution activities visible at all levels to build trust among teams and across the organization.
 - o **Program Execution:** Focus on working systems and business outcomes.
 - o **Leadership:** Model the values and principles of SAFe.

- **Scrum of Scrums:** is a technique for integrating the work of multiple, smaller Scrum teams working on the same project or solution. Coordination among teams is critical to ensuring the deliverables from each team can be integrated into one larger, cohesive deliverable. Scrum of scrums involve the following elements:
 - A group of at least 12 or more people divided into Scrum Teams of five to ten people each
 - Scrum of Scrums meetings, which are held once a week, twice a week, or daily.
 - A **Scrum Master** or designated “ambassador” for each team that participates in the Scrum of Scrums meetings and a **Scrum of Scrums Master** who focuses on the overall Scrum process across multiple teams
 - Sprint Planning, Sprint Review, and Sprint Retrospective meetings
- **Large Scale Scrum (LeSS):** is a framework that aims to maximize the Scrum team’s ability to deliver value and reduce waste in larger organizations. The ten LeSS principles are:
 - **Large-scale Scrum is Scrum:** Apply the values and principles of Scrum to a larger team.
 - **Empirical process control:** Inspect, adapt, and learn from experience to improve processes.
 - **Transparency:** Ensure clarity and accessibility across a project.
 - **More with less:** Create only necessary processes, roles, artifacts, and waste when scaling.
 - **Whole-product focus:** Think holistically about the product, making sure that all the parts serve the whole.
 - **Customer-centric:** Keep the customer’s needs and values at the heart of your process.
 - **Continuous improvement towards perfection:** Improve the product—and your process—during every single Sprint.
 - **Systems thinking:** Think about the system as a whole; Don’t get lost in the details.
 - **Lean thinking:** Seek continuous improvement, aim for perfection, and respect people.
 - **Queuing theory:** Embrace the Lean principles of “flow,’ manage queue size,” and “minimize multitasking” to keep delivering value.
- **Disciplined Agile Delivery (DAD):** is a hybrid approach that combines the strategies from various Agile frameworks, including Kanban, LeSS, Lean Development, Extreme Programming, Agile Modeling, and more. DAD guides people through the process-related decisions that frameworks like SAFe and Scrum of Scrums leave open. DAD is organized into four “layers”:
 - **Foundations** discusses the principles, guidelines, Agile concepts, roles and team structure definitions, and Way of Working (WoW).
 - **Disciplined DevOps** ensures that solutions are delivered to customers effectively and safely, with data and security management always at the forefront.
 - **Value Streams** ensures that solutions are aligned with the organization's business strategy, connecting customers, sales, and portfolio management to the framework.

- **Disciplined Agile Enterprise (DAE)** connects the industry marketplace with corporate governance and larger enterprise activities.
- **Spotify Model:** The model began as a description of how Spotify overcame the challenges of scaling Agile. By focusing their efforts on culture, team autonomy, communication, accountability, and quality, they increased their agility over time. Spotify's approach has had a huge impact on workflows and team structures across the tech world. Some of the key components include:
 - **Squads:** Like Scrum teams, Squads are autonomous teams of 6–12 people working toward the same outcome. All Squads include a coach (similar to a Scrum Master) and a Product Owner.
 - **Tribes:** When multiple Squads work on the same feature area, they form a Tribe of 40–150 people. Each Tribe has a Tribe Lead who fosters collaboration and coordination.
 - **Chapters:** Squads may be autonomous, but specialists (e.g., JavaScript developers) should still align across an organization. Chapters establish best practices and, where necessary, set standards.
 - **Guilds:** Any group of people interested in a certain topic can form a Guild, where people with shared interests can come together as a community.

Best practices for scaling agile:

- Treat scaling models like SAFe, Scrum of Scrums, LeSS, etc., as general frameworks, not instruction manuals.
- Different situations require different solutions. It's okay to mix and match elements from multiple frameworks, as long as you apply the principles and values of the Agile Manifesto.
- Don't try to scale without prior Agile experience. Going straight from Waterfall to scaled Agile can be risky without a knowledgeable guide.
- Finally, and most importantly, don't scale if it isn't necessary. The larger your team, the more complex and difficult your project becomes.

Agile project management **position**. These types of jobs might show up on job boards as Agile Project Manager, Scrum Master, IT Agile Project Manager, or a DevOps Project Manager.

Some questions you should ask during a project management position **interview**:

- how supportive is the management here towards blending project management approaches?
- What's the first thing I should know about the culture here?
- And how often will I get to hear about the needs of our users or customers?
- And what would a typical day look like for me if I were to take on this position?

How to introduce agile to a team:

- start small
- listen to feedback
- be strategic.
- find allies.

You need to submit 80 applications to get your first offer, if you make some reasonable calculations.

Applying project management:

- **Strategic thinking:** involves analyzing documentation and talking with stakeholders to inform decisions based on the information available to you.

common cause of project failure:

- misalignment between you and your stakeholders on the vision for the project
- misalignment on the project details between stakeholders

When presenting project charters to stakeholders:

- collect feedback
- identify where there are misalignments.
- Then you can make changes to address those misalignments.

Document misalignments and resolutions!!

An **appendix** is a section of additional content at the end of a document. A **time stamp** includes the date, and sometimes the time, of when the new content was created or added to the document.

common cause of project failure is misalignment among stakeholders about the project details.

Benchmarking: which refers to evaluating success against the standard.

Benefits are the expected gains of a project.

Costs refer to the money spent on project tasks and the prices of things like time, resources, and labor.

budget is an estimate of the amount of money allocated to complete the project.

A list of benefits can help you identify potential project goals you might have missed.

A list of costs will include items the organization will have to pay for in order to get the job done, like the price of labor or materials.

Scope refers to the boundaries of the project.

Stakeholder management is the process of maintaining good relationships with the people who have the most influence on your work.

Stakeholder management during project initiation:

- **Identify all the stakeholders at the beginning of your project or initiative.** Get everyone involved as early as possible to set clear expectations, responsibilities, and boundaries.
- **Keep the project vision clear.** The **project vision** describes the need the project is fulfilling.
- **Equip your stakeholders with user-friendly resources at all times.** This could mean creating a **one-pager** (a one-page document that provides an overview of your project) or weekly status report with the latest information and links to the main project artifacts.

Stakeholder management throughout the project life cycle:

- Find out what stakeholders care about and why.
- Adjust your communication frequency and approach based on stakeholder roles and preferences.
- Enlist the help of senior stakeholders when necessary.
- Once stakeholders have a vested interest, bring project problems to them.

persuasion and negotiation: are constructive tools you can use to enhance communication, clarify wants and needs, and achieve workable solutions for everyone involved. Being skilled at persuasion and negotiation will also boost your level of influence.

It's important that you view the people you're negotiating with as your colleagues and peers, not as opponents.

Mutual benefit is when all parties involved gain some kind of benefit or advantage.

Tips for navigating scope with stakeholders:

- Understand motivations: Before your discussion, consider each stakeholder's motivations for wanting to adjust the project's scope.
- Set the scene: Start the discussion with a reflection on why you are meeting.
- Listen first: Hear what your stakeholders have to say before you present your views.
- Ask questions to define goals: Be thorough and ask as many questions as you feel necessary to understand what the stakeholder wants.
- Explain the "Why" before the "What": When attempting to persuade stakeholders—or anyone, for that matter—to see things your way, explain the reasons for your request *before* describing what you want.
- Do not oversell: Sometimes it's best to state your case and give others some time to respond.
- Be creative: Working to find alternative solutions can quickly turn a heavy negotiation into an inspiring team effort.
- **Do not make it personal.** Always focus on what is good for the project.
- **Seek a win-win outcome.** Finally, consider what it will take for the other side to be satisfied.

mutually beneficial agreement. This is an agreement that benefits all parties involved.

Best practices for reaching a mutually beneficial agreement:

- **Share information.**
- **Ask questions and listen actively to responses.**
- **Propose multiple options whenever possible.**

A **coalition** is a temporary alliance or partnering of individuals or groups in order to achieve a common purpose or to engage in a joint activity.

When **two or more** people advocate together for an idea, they're able to exert more influence than if they attempted to act **alone.**

Benefits of a coalition:

- Boosts your credibility.
- The people in your coalition helps you find common ground and provide evidence.
- Can connect emotionally if someone on the coalition knows a stakeholder.

Persuasive coalition request:

- Clearly state the issue.
- Ask the person for their support.
- refer to that person's sources of power or interest, you identified.

A **project plan** is useful for any project, big or small, since it helps you document the scope, tasks, milestones, budget, and overall activities in order to keep the project on track.

To create a project plan:

- Start by reviewing the goals in the project charter.
- Make a list of all the tasks, milestones.
- For more information review emails and previous project plans.

A deliverable in the project charter could be considered as a milestone, and the work required to finish this deliverable could be broken down into tasks.

Get more information by reviewing previous project plans:

- ask a colleague with experience launching other products for the same company to share their project plan.
- ask colleagues about unrelated projects that also had construction components.
- provide helpful inspiration as you create your own list of tasks.
- identify possible task durations, subject matter experts, and even suppliers that may be helpful to your project.

Domain knowledge refers to knowledge of a specific industry, topic, or activity.

Another key to success when working on an unfamiliar project is knowing where to find useful information that can help you increase your domain knowledge.

Having **industry knowledge** can also save you time on future projects within that industry, since you won't have to ask as many questions or do as much research.

Online research can help increase your knowledge of industry terms, techniques, processes, and more,

Tips for project research:

- Try searching online for news coverage of similar projects at other companies.
- search online for research on topics related to your project.
- research similar projects in other industries.
- review the list of tasks that you've identified so far and research the specifics of executing that work.

Populating your plan with a set of tasks can indicate to future employers that:

- you're able to identify key areas of work based on documentation, research, conversations, and more.
- you're able to synthesize these tasks into a single, organized document, which is a critical part of project management.

Discover task through conversations with your project team:

- One way to discover more tasks is to hold a group brainstorm session with team members who will likely work on those tasks.
- hold one-on-one conversations with team members about tasks they'll likely be responsible for completing.
- leverage the expertise of your teammates to discover what you don't know and to fill in gaps in your list of tasks.

After identifying, stakeholder's interest and power prepare for the conversation:

- Gather information ahead of time.
- Outline clear questions you need answers to.
- Present your research and your current list of tasks
- Have conversations with stakeholders

Conversations usually contain more info than you need to create a list of tasks, and the right level of detail you need to include in your project will vary from project to project and team to team.

To determine task priority:

- Basic order of operations / natural task sequence
- Dependencies or prerequisites

Determining milestones:

- Identify point in the project plan where you and your team can evaluate the work been done so far.
- Identify project tasks that you or your stakeholders have a particular interest in.
- Identify tasks that carry a high risk or signal the completion of a phase or a major task.

Time estimation:

Strategies for getting accurate time estimates from experts:

- Check their understanding of the task.
- ask for estimates of the sub-steps and make note of them.
- discuss the assumptions the expert might be making when they give you an estimate.
- ask the task expert to consider how likely it might be that all or some of these assumptions might not work out and how that might impact their estimate.
- compare the expert's estimates against the actual time spent on similar tasks in previous work.

Three-point estimating is used to help determine the most realistic time estimate for a task. It uses optimistic and pessimistic calculations, meaning calculations based on the best-case and worst-case scenarios.

Three-point estimating:

- Each task receives three time estimates:
 - o Optimistic: estimate assumes the best-case scenario: Issues will not occur.
 - o Most-likely: estimate assumes some issues might occur. is based on how long the task usually takes under normal circumstances.
 - o Pessimistic: estimate assumes that issues will definitely occur. This is where everything that could go wrong does go wrong.
- Each estimate indicates the projected amount of time a task will take under that category

Determining a final estimate:

- examine the best-and worst-case scenario timing
- compare these with the most likely scenario.
- build in a buffer that accounts for risks that are likely but still keeps the project progressing at an efficient rate.

Three-points time estimation formulas:

- The triangular distribution: weight of each estimate in this equation is identical it works by taking the sum of all estimates and dividing on three.

It looks something like : $\frac{\text{optimistic} + \text{mostlikely} + \text{pessimistic}}{3}$

- The Beta (PERT) distribution: is a weighted average. The most likely estimate receives a multiplier of four, while the overall divisor is increased to six. the Beta (PERT) Distribution has been proven to be more accurate than three-point estimating and is often used to calculate both cost and time estimates.

And it looks something like: $\frac{\text{optimistic} + (4 \times \text{mostlikely}) + \text{pessimistic}}{6}$

confidence level rating: indicates how confident you are in an estimate's accuracy. If you are not sure about your confidence level communicate with your team, and if you have many lows in the confidence level rating communicate the schedule weakness to the stakeholders.

Ways to determine a confidence rating:

- Use the three-way technique.
- Poll your team.
 - o Get a percentage for how confident they are
 - o Define categories

Implementing a system that accounts for those unknowns and ensures an accurate picture of project costs means everyone will be better off over the long term.

Techniques specific to negotiating time estimates:

- Say “NO” without saying “NO”.
 - o Ask open ended questions like:
 - how would you like me to proceed?
 - How can we solve this problem?
 - What can I do to help?
- Focus on interests, not positions.
 - o try to identify the other person's interests, their basic needs, wants, and motivations around completing a certain task.
- Present mutually beneficial options. Here you and the expert are disagreeing on the estimate so, ask some open-ended questions like the ones above to get an agreeable estimate.
- Insist on objective criteria.
 - o Base criteria on neutral information like market value, research findings, previously documented experience, or laws and regulations.
 - o agree in advance about which objective criteria to consult, and then to use the information to determine your estimates.

Empathy is the ability to understand and feel what others are feeling.

Asking questions about how long a task will take could make some people feel insecure. They might feel like you don't trust them, that you think they're not competent, that you believe you know more than they do about their own work, and so on.

Micromanaging is when a manager too closely observes, controls, or continuously reminds the people they're managing of the work they've been assigned.

Ways to bring empathy to your conversation:

- Listen with curiosity.
- Repeat what you think you heard
- Connect with their experience
- Recognize judgments.
- Recognize buffering
- Avoid distractions

Quality management plan:

- quality standards,
- evaluation questions,
- feedback surveys

Benefits of quality management:

- delivering a quality product,
- decreasing overhead,
- increasing collaboration and ongoing reviews.

Overarching quality management plan:

- documents all the information needed to effectively manage quality throughout the project life cycle.
- defines the policies, processes, and criteria for project quality, as well as the roles and responsibilities for carrying out the quality management plan.

Quality: means making sure that you deliver what you say you will and that you do so as efficiently as you can.

Quality standards are the requirements and specifications that your product or service must meet in order to be considered successful by your organization and the customer.

When working on quality, the resources to consult:

- project documents like
 - o The business case
 - o project charter.
- conversations with experts and stakeholders
- industry research.

Common quality standard categories:

- functionality,
- design,
- Safety.
- ease of use,
- productivity,
- effectiveness,
- customer satisfaction.

quality assurance consists of reviewing processes to evaluate whether or not your project is delivering an acceptable level of quality.

evaluation involves observing, measuring, and then comparing your findings to a set of agreed upon criteria. It is a form of research designed to promote learning and inform decisions.

quality assurance are:

- beta testing,
- internal checklists,
- feedback surveys.

Reasons to use evaluation:

- To improve
- To judge: whether something is working the way it was intended.
- To learn: what things made the project run as intended, how it can be replicated, and how challenges could be overcome in the future.

Evaluation process:

- Determine the reasons for evaluating
- Write out evaluation questions. Evaluation question: is a key question about the outcomes, impact, and/or effectiveness of your project or program. And there are two main categories of evaluation questions:
 - o How to improve, like:
 - How can we improve?
 - What is working and what's not working?
 - Which goals are being met?
 - Who is benefiting?
 - What are the most common participant reactions?
 - o Help you measure and compare, like:
 - What were the results?
 - Were there unintended outcomes?
 - What were the costs and benefits?
 - Are there any lessons to be learned?
 - Should we continue?

Effective evaluation questions meet the following criteria:

- They address stakeholder or user values, interests, and concerns
- They relate to the purpose of the project and of evaluation
- They're worth answering and are important for the project and beyond
- and they're practical and feasible to answer with available resources

Evaluation indicators reveal the specific type of data that needs to be collected to help you answer your evaluation questions. Evaluation indicators take your evaluation question and determine the specific type of response you're aiming for. They provide pathways for answering your evaluation questions.

Surveying:

Being able to develop a survey and write survey questions is important because it demonstrates your ability to understand the goals of your project and assess how your stakeholders and users value the project.

Surveys: are tools you can use to evaluate and measure the quality of a project's process, goal, or deliverable.

Benefits of surveys:

- help you understand what's working and what's not working.

- Surveys assess the criteria you want to evaluate.
- provide you with data that will point out whether you've met your quality standards.

Survey development process:

- develop evaluation questions
- define your evaluation indicators
- determine what type of survey to design and questions to ask

a **survey question** is designed to collect data, which can help you answer your evaluation questions.

Types of survey questions:

- Open-ended: Open-ended questions require more than one-word answers, such as yes or no.
- Closed-ended: questions can be answered with a single response, like yes or no or true or false or selecting a single answer from a list.

Tips for creating good survey questions:

- make sure your questions are asking what you mean to ask
- Each question should be specific and address only one measurable aspect.
- Be careful not to make assumptions about your respondents.
- Make sure that your questions don't provide too much detail or information

Evaluation presentation:

- Consider your audience:
 - o what's most meaningful to them?
 - o How much time they have?
- Present the same data in different ways
- Create a detailed evaluation report
 - o summarize the information into the most appropriate format for a given audience.

Common **reporting styles:**

- summary sheet
- slide-based presentation

By filtering and analyzing, you become familiar with the results, the respondents, and what those results mean in regards to project quality.

start **analyzing data** to present by:

- look for trends, patterns, and anomalies.
- share this process with some of your team members. Taking turns sharing what you think the data means.

A great way to present an evaluation is through a story.

Storytelling is the process of turning facts into narrative to communicate something to your audience.

An evaluation is:

- More than a raw data report.
- It needs to reflect what the data means.
- explain how it informs a response to the evaluation questions.

What to include in your evaluation presentation

- **Introduction:** a summary of your presentation and includes an overview of the project's goals and desired outcomes
- **What is being evaluated and why:** where you will state the purpose of the evaluation.
 - o State the goal, milestone, or deliverable that is being evaluated and the quality standards that were defined for that aspect of the project.
 - o Include the evaluation questions and indicators that were used to evaluate each quality standard.
- **Evaluation findings:** state your findings. **Pro tip:** Visualize the data with graphs or charts to quickly convey the message of the findings.
- **Conclusion with recommendations:** state your findings again and propose a couple of recommendations for how to apply the findings to the next phase of the project.

Additional tips

- **Tailor communications to stakeholders:** When it comes to communicating important milestones to stakeholders, consider whom you are presenting to. Tailor your presentation to your audience in a way that they will understand and enjoy.
- **Start with an interesting hook:** Begin your presentation with an ice breaker, joke, or an interesting visual aid to get your stakeholders' attention right away.
- **Use visuals throughout your presentation:** The use of visuals creates interest and keeps the audience engaged in your presentation.

Benefits of retrospectives:

- encourage team building
- facilitate improved collaboration
- promote positive changes

your role as project manager to facilitate a respectful and productive retrospective discussion that recognizes successes and areas for improvement.

Techniques to **encourage participation** in retrospectives:

- create a safe environment for the team. Maybe by adopting a policy of what's said here stays here, what's learned here leaves
- model the kind of participation you'd like to elicit from your team

- pose a group question and ask for individual responses.
- review the project timeline.

Accountability benefits:

- encourages the team to think holistically about mistakes and challenges.
- identify solutions for the future.
- encourages ownership

Accountability and blame are two very different things, and only accountability belongs in a retrospective.

Blame shuts people down instead of empowering them to share honestly.

Techniques to **encourage accountability**:

- come prepared with specific challenges to discuss as a group
- turn team complaints into smart action items.
- push the team to identify its role in creating a given challenge.

Constructive criticism is a respectful form of feedback that is intended to help the recipient improve a piece of work.

Techniques to **address negativity** during a retrospective:

- aim to set a positive tone at the start of the meeting
- Determine how you'll set the tone of the meeting.
- try anticipating any potential negativity by meeting one on one with team members before the retrospective happens.
 - o Does this person feel insecure about the value they add to this team?
 - o Does this person receive negative feedback on the quality of their work?
- consider asking team members individually to share their thoughts.
- call a meeting break.

Communicating project problems is a part of your job as a project manager.

project managers synthesizes relevant information from multiple sources into a coherent summary that clearly communicates the issue.

Synthesizing requires gathering information from multiple sources and using those points to help form your own analysis.

Objectives and Key Results are a tool for organization-wide goal setting.

OKRs can be a kind of shared language for an organization.

best practices to make sure your email doesn't get ignored:

- think about what's most important to your stakeholder.
- Identify how a problem will impact your organization as a whole and ensure that you clearly communicate that impact within the first two sentences of your email.
- write a clear subject line
- include language in your subject line that indicates what you'd like your stakeholder to do upon reading your email.
- keep the body of the email brief and to the point.
- consider including hyperlinks or attachments with the information in your email.
- proofread it for misspellings, grammatical errors and inaccurate hyperlinks.

The **closeout report** is a great opportunity to compile all links and documentation into one place, a practice we like to call: good **project hygiene**.

Closeout report benefits:

- confirms the project is done.
- summarizes deliverables, success metrics, feedback, lessons learned and next steps
- serves as a reference document for the organization.

An **effective** closeout report:

- helps ensure that everyone is satisfied with the work that was done.
- finalizes the efforts of the team and lets people move on to new projects and tasks.
- increases the impact of the team's work through communication with other people who may not have been as involved in the project.

A project closeout report **includes**:

- project summary,
- methodology,
- performance baseline,
- outcomes,
- lessons learned
- next steps
- project documentation archive.

Impact reporting:

created for senior stakeholders or project sponsors who weren't involved in the day-to-day details of the project.

Impact report can **help** you to:

- analyze results to adapt and improve services.
- Motivate staff and senior stakeholders by celebrating achievements.
- Build trust and credibility with supporters, sponsors, funders, and anyone benefiting from the project.
- Share lessons with similar organizations.

Executive summary:

- a few sentences to a paragraph that describe the project's purpose and outcome.
- provides an overview of the main points of a larger report. It's written to share with the stakeholders who might not have time to review the entire report.

executive summary should aim to answer questions like:

- How effectively was the project delivered?
- What did we learn from it?

Topics to include in the project summary:

- Project vision
- Key accomplishments.
- Lessons learned

Create your **elevator pitch**:

- **elevator pitch** is a quick professional summary of yourself.
- To craft a strong elevator pitch, break it down into three parts:
 - o who you are,
 - o what skills and experiences you have,
 - o what you want.
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